

D6.1 Life cycle assessment and recycling options of Fatigue4Light solutions

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Executive summary

Fatigue4Light project aims at developing lightweighting solutions to show the benefits of EVs (BEV, HEV and pHEV) in material and energy consumption as well as environmental and economic impact, preserving fatigue and general performance of chassis parts.

In this report, Objective number 10 of the project by conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) for all chassis parts demonstrators. In addition, recycling solutions are also studied.

General methodological aspects of LCA and LCC methodologies are adjusted to be applied on the demonstrators including all life cycle stages of a vehicle from cradle-to-cradle.

LCA results for all demonstrators prove Fatigue4Light solutions as more beneficial solutions from an environmental point of view. As expected, use stage is the most dominant stage from an environmental point of view and lighter solutions have lesser energy consumption during the use stage. Regardless of the manufacturing and assembly stage, use stage is of great relevance for BEV, HEV and pHEV options.

Economic assessment also proves Fatigue4Light solutions as more economically efficient. Although hybrid solutions are still at lab scale and therefore less efficient than any other solution, even when compared to the other Lab-demonstrators.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicle</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>FU</i>	<i>Functional Unit</i>
<i>LCA</i>	<i>Life Cycle Assessment</i>
<i>LCC</i>	<i>Life Cycle Cost</i>
<i>LCI</i>	<i>Life Cycle Inventory</i>
<i>LCIA</i>	<i>Life Cycle Impact Assessment</i>
<i>BEV</i>	<i>Battery Electric Vehicle</i>
<i>HEV</i>	<i>Hybrid Electric Vehicle</i>
<i>pHEV</i>	<i>Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle</i>

Introduction

Fatigue4Light project aims to address the challenge of lightweighting in the transportation industry by introducing specially developed materials solutions with high fatigue performance (AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials), the development of new computer modelling with high fatigue prediction accuracy and new experimental methodologies that reduce the testing time for new materials for vehicles.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the lightweight alternatives, an economic and environmental assessment will be conducted. This assessment will compare the baseline scenario, which uses conventional materials, with the new lightweight solutions considered in the project. The assessment will be carried out using a life cycle perspective, focusing on the raw materials extraction and transformation, as well as the use and end-of-life phases of the different demonstrators.

The goal of the assessment is to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental and economic benefits of the different materials in EVs. By reducing the weight of vehicles, these new materials can improve the EV's efficiency and reduce their environmental impact, while also reducing production costs and improving the overall economic viability of EVs. The results of the assessment will be used to guide the development and deployment of the lightweight solutions evaluated by the Fatigue4Light project, with the ultimate goal of improving the sustainability and affordability of EVs.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time nor content deviation.

1 LCA Methodology

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology is commonly used to identify, describe, and evaluate the environmental aspects and possible effects of a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle. This involves creating a list of relevant inputs and outputs of a product system to assess its potential environmental impacts. Through the analysis of the inventory, combined with the impact assessment, an interpretation of the results in relation to the study's objectives is offered.

To obtain a comprehensive study of all inputs and outputs involved, the life cycle is typically divided into stages such as raw material extraction and manufacturing, product use, and end-of-life management. The international standards ISO 14040(ISO/TC 207 2006a) and 14044(ISO/TC 207 2006b) outline the fundamental structure and principles of LCA methodology, including four interconnected phases: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation. Moreover, the SPE-14040-1475 standard ("GUIDELINES_LCA_AUTO_PARTS_CSA_Group_2014.Pdf," n.d.) developed by the CSA group, establishes the requirements for conducting comparative LCA of automotive parts incorporating weight changes due to changes in material composition, manufacturing technology, or part geometry.

LCA is an iterative and holistic process that requires revisiting many of the phases to incorporate new findings, changes in study goals and data availability. Figure 1 presents these phases and their interrelationships.

Figure 1. LCA framework

1.1 Goal and scope

The first step in an LCA study is the goal and scope definition phase, which is of paramount importance as it sets the basis for the entire study. While modifications can be made to the scope later on, it is best to establish it as the starting point for the study given the holistic nature of LCA. The scope outlines the system's performance, including the selected function(s) to be reflected by the study's goal, any limitations, allocation procedures (if necessary), data requirements, quality, main assumptions, and impact categories to be evaluated.

The functional unit is essential in quantifying the function of the study, and it should be coherent with the system's goal and scope. The definition of the functional unit determines the fluxes, and it is followed by the definition of the reference flux. Both the functional unit and reference flow must be clearly defined and measurable.

System boundaries describe the processes within the system, and their determination should align with the study's goal. Whenever a life cycle stage or process step is ruled out, it should not significantly modify the results, and the decision to do so must be clearly explained and justified.

1.2 Inventory analysis

In this phase, the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) is created by collecting data on all inputs and outputs in reference to the functional unit. This includes a compilation of all extractions from the environment such as energy and material inputs, as well as releases to the environment like products, wastes, and emissions to the atmosphere, water, and soil. The resulting LCI provides a comprehensive list of all inputs and outputs related to the product or system being studied.

To ensure accurate and reliable results, data quality should be prioritized. Primary data obtained directly from the producer or originator should be used whenever possible, while secondary data can be used to fill in any gaps. In cases where reliable foreground data is not available, reasonable assumptions may be necessary. Additionally, trustworthy databases and scientific literature can also be utilized to supplement the study.

1.3 Impact assessment

During the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), the inventory is translated into potential environmental impacts, and the assessments are categorized into mandatory and optional operations. The mandatory elements include:

- Selecting impact categories, category indicators, and models, where environmental effects are identified based on various factors, such as the study's objectives and the sector being examined.
- Assigning LCIA results (classification), which uses category indicators that match the effects of inventory elements with selected impact categories.
- Calculating category indicator results (characterization), which involves translating the matches found in the classification step into potential environmental impacts by applying characterization factors derived from the category indicators and the characterization model.
- Conducting data quality analysis.

1.4 Interpretation

During the interpretation phase, the study results are presented and analysed, considering factors such as contribution analysis, relevance reasoning, data quality limitations, and critical review. This stage provides a comprehensive assessment of the study's conclusions, highlighting any limitations in the results and offering recommendations based on the findings.

By conducting a systematic evaluation, it is possible to identify opportunities for minimizing the negative effects of the system being studied, while also avoiding burden shifting between different stages of the life cycle or impact categories.

2 LCC Methodology

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) serves as an evaluation of the complete expenses linked with a product's life cycle and can work in conjunction with environmental and social considerations to assess the sustainability of the product. Any entity involved in the product life cycle, including suppliers, producers, users/consumers, and end-of-life actors, can apply the LCC methodology. Consequently, this tool proves beneficial for determining appropriate actions and recognizing difficulties from different viewpoints, whether it be a product/service developer or a consumer.

LCC Methodology application is adapted from ISO 15686-5:2017 Part 5: Life-cycle costing (ISO/TC 59 2017).

LCC allows for the comparison of different alternatives by considering their cash flows, initial investments, and time frames. The purpose of LCC is to provide quantitative analysis of costs throughout the lifetime of each demonstrator, which can then be used as a basis for decision-making or evaluation processes.

3 Scenario definition and approach

Lab-scale demonstrator’s environmental and economic performance is evaluated through LCA and LCC respectively. The lab-scale demonstrators developed in WP1 and manufactured with selected materials and with the currently used materials (reference materials) are the different scenarios to be studied in WP6 and more specifically their environmental and economic performance. Table 1 summarizes the scenarios that are studied within Fatigue4Light project.

Table 1. Studied scenarios.

Demonstrator	Reference material	F4L Material
Lower control arm	CP800	CP980 and Hybrid (Al+GFRP)
Cross beam member	S355	22MnB5
Wheel	DP600	CP800
L-shape demonstrator	DP600 S355/420LA	CP800 CP980 AA6181 22MnB5 AISI 410S Hybrid (GFRP)

LCA and LCC analysis of CP980 is not included in this report for the low control arm demonstrator because the weight reduction analysis has not been completed. All calculations performed for the CP800 are valid for the CP980-based solution as the processes are the same and the only difference is the weight.

Goal and scope

A cradle-to-cradle perspective has been applied in the environmental and cost studies of Fatigue4Light demonstrators. Three life cycle stages have been identified: First stage incorporates raw material extraction, manufacturing, and assembly; second stage includes the use stage of the EV; and third stage comprises the end-of-life (Figure 2). Moreover, Figure 3 depicts the system boundaries (including the three life cycle stages), which states the processes that are included in the study.

System boundaries include the production of the demonstrator, the use stage and the end-of-life management. In this line, main inputs considered are: energy and materials.

Figure 2. Fatigue4Light LCA Scope

Figure 3. System boundaries

Functional unit is determined as the driving distance of 1 km. Considering a lifetime driving distance of 180.000km according to the EEA Report (European Environment Agency 2018) in conjunction with energy consumption depicted on Table 2, also based the same Report.

Table 2. Energy consumption during use stage for BEV

Type	Typical battery weight (kg)	Typical vehicle weight (kg)	Energy consumption (kWh/100km)	Lifetime driving distance (km)	Energy consumption per kg of EV (kWh/100km kg)	Energy consumed during lifetime (kWh/vehicle)	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)
Luxury car	553	2,100	21	180,000	0.010	37800	18.00
Large car	393	1,750	19	180,000	0.011	34200	19.54

Medium car	253	1,500	17	180,000	0.011	30600	20.40
Mini car	177	1,100	15	180,000	0.014	27000	24.55

Average fuel and energy consumption for BEV, HEV and pHEV (based on previous table and references) are presented in Table 3. Considering electric powertrains as 100% for BEV, 30% for HEV and 50% for pHEV according to Tagliaferri et al. (2016) (Tagliaferri et al. 2016) and fuel consumption for HEV and PHEV as 50.04 mL/km, based on Ecoinvent 2.2 (Spielmann, M., Bauer, C., Dones 2007; Swiss Centre for Life Cycle Inventories 2014).

Table 3. Energy and fuel consumption

BEV	ICEV	HEV (30%)		PHEV (50%)	
Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (mL/kg)	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (mL/kg)	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (mL/kg)
20.09	5585.86	6.03	3910.10	10.05	2792.93

End-of-life has been considered based on Europe statistics published by Eurostat (Statistics 2021) and is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. End-of-life waste management

WASTE MANAGEMENT	Disposal	Recovery	Energy Recovery	Recycling
% End-of-life vehicles by waste management operations	4%	48%	3%	44%

4 LCI

4.1 LCI for LCA

The lower control arm demonstrator has been studied in its conventional and Fatigue4Light architecture. Inventory for the conventional lower control arm is presented on Table 5 and for the Fatigue4Light on Table 6. Packaging was estimated based on the weight of the demonstrator.

Table 5. LCI Conventional Lower Control Arm

CONVENTIONAL LOWER CONTROL ARM		2.111		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Blanking	CP800	3.36	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.222	kWh	Input

	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	1.275	kg	Output
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	1.344	tkm	Input
Forming	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0.020	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.525	kWh	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	tkm	Input
Shot peening	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.184	kWh	Input
Sleeve welding	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.014	kg	Input
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	0.061	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.786	kWh	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.003	tkm	Input
Painting	Alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state {RER} market for alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state Cut-off, U	0.012	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	tkm	Input
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.001	p	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.002	kg	Input
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.016	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input

Table 6. LCI Fatigue4Light Lower Control Arm

F4L LOWER CONTROL ARM		1.38 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Blanking	AA6181	2	kg	Input
	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0.656	kg	Input
	Sand {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.064	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.50	kWh	Input
	Aluminium (waste treatment) {GLO} recycling of aluminium Cut-off, U	2.158	kg	Output
	Inert waste {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of inert waste, sanitary landfill Cut-off, U	0.064	kg	Output
	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of wastewater, average, capacity 1E9l/year Cut-off, U	0.001	m3	Output
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	4.343	tkm	Input
AI Wash	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.808	tkm	Input
	Soap {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	53	g	Input
	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0.150	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.421	kWh	Input
	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of wastewater, average, capacity 1E9l/year Cut-off, U	0.000	m3	Output
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	0.386	tkm	Input
Heat Treatment	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	tkm	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.800	kWh	Input
Pre-preg	Glass fibre {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	170.0	g	Input
	Epoxy resin, liquid {RER} market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, U	250.0	g	Input
	Urea formaldehyde resin {RER} market for urea formaldehyde resin Cut-off, U	57.5	g	Input
	Ethylenediamine {RER} market for ethylenediamine Cut-off, U	12.5	g	Input
	Ethylenediamine {RER} market for ethylenediamine Cut-off, U	30.0	g	Input

	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	20.0	g	Input
	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {RER} production Cut-off, U	50.0	g	Input
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	25.0	g	Input
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	20.0	g	Input
	Glued laminated timber, average glue mix {Europe without Switzerland} market for glued laminated timber, average glue mix Cut-off, U	10.0	g	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.18	kWh	Input
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, with energy recovery Cut-off, U	315.0	g	Output
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	0.434	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.006	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.405	tkm	Input
Hybrid LCA	Textile, nonwoven polyester {GLO} market for textile, nonwoven polyester Cut-off, U	5	g	Input
	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	50	g	Input
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	30	g	Input
	Sealing tape, aluminium/PE, 50 mm wide {RER} production Cut-off, U	1	m	Input
	Chemical, organic {GLO} fraction 1 from naphtha separation to generic market for Cut-off, U	200	g	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	13	kWh	Input
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, with energy recovery Cut-off, U	331	g	Output
LCA cut	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.130	kWh	Input
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, with energy recovery Cut-off, U	112.0	g	Output
Bonding	Epoxy resin, liquid {RER} market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, U	60.0	g	Input
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	30.0	g	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	-1.22	kWh	Input
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, with energy recovery Cut-off, U	30.0	g	Output
LCA B cut	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.1	kWh	Input
Al parts	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	270	kWh	Input

It is worth noting that for the hybrid Lower Control Arm the assumptions included on Table 7, were considered.

Table 7. Hybrid Lower Control Arm assumptions

Assumptions Hybrid LCA		Comment
2. Al Blank Cut	Water	Equipment is too big (industrial size) and the water and abrasive is filled in the equipment according to its full capacity. The electricity value was taken from a similar equipment, and the full capacity kWh was calculated according to the used time for our unity (1 part =232 g).
	Abrasive	
	Electricity	
3. Al wash	Detergent	Equipment is industrial (70 l total capacity) and the water is reused for others washings. The Unit is only 100 g (2 plates).
	Water	
	Electricity	
4. Al heat treat	Electricity	Equipment was too old, no information was found about the Watts - similar equipment was found at internet.

5. Prepreg	Electricity	Equipment was too old, no information was found about the Watts - similar equipment was found at internet.
6. Hybrid LCA	Electricity	No information about Watts was found in the equipment. A similar model was found at internet.
7. LCA Cut	Electricity	No information about Watts was found in the equipment. A similar model was found at internet.
8. Bonding	Detergent	Equipment is industrial (70 l total capacity) and the water is reused for others washings. The Unit is only 100 g (2 plates).
	Water	
	Electricity	
9. LCA-B Cut	Electricity	No information about Watts was found in the equipment. A similar model was found at internet.
10. Al parts	Electricity	This step was not performed yet, so we just have approximated values
	Labor time	

Inventory for the Cross Beam Member for the Conventional demonstrator is presented in Table 8, while Table 9 presents the Fatigue4Light Cross Beam Member. Packaging was estimated based on the weight of the demonstrator.

Table 8. LCI Conventional Cross Beam Member

CONVENTIONAL CROSS BEAM MEMBER		18.9 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Blanking	S355MC steel	21	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.022	kWh	Input
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	23.100	tkm	Input
Stamping	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.112	kWh	Input
Shot blasting	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.980	kWh	Input
Laser	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.161	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.700	kWh	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.008	tkm	Input
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.008	kg	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.022	kg	Input
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.009	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	tkm	Input

Table 9. LCI Fatigue4Light Cross Beam Member

F4L CROSS BEAM MEMBER		12.6 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Blanking	22MnB5	14	kg	Input
	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.105	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.700	kWh	Input
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	15.400	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.005	tkm	Input
Furnace	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	3.001	kWh	Input
Stamping	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.021	kWh	Input
Shot blasting	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.980	kWh	Input
Laser	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.071	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.450	kWh	Input

	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	tkm	Input
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.006	p	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.015	kg	Input
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.006	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	tkm	Input

For the Wheel demonstrator, conventional LCI is presented in Table 10, while Table 11 presents the LCI for Fatigue4Light Wheel.

Table 10. LCI Conventional Wheel

CONVENTIONAL WHEEL		10 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Rim line	DP600	5	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.630	kWh	Input
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	0.620	m3	Input
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	5.331	tkm	Input
Disc line	DP600	6.749	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.360	kWh	Input
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	0.280	m3	Input
	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	2.080	kg	Output
Welding	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	6.749	tkm	Input
	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.031	kg	Input
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	0.024	kg	Input
	Carbon dioxide, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.005	kg	Input
Flowforming	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.003	tkm	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.68	kWh	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.635	kWh	Input
	Sandblasting	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.012	kg
Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U		0.4	kWh	Input
Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U		0.001	tkm	Input
Cataphoresys process		Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.010	kg
	Non-ionic surfactant {GLO} market for non-ionic surfactant Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Sulfuric acid {RER} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Chemical, inorganic {GLO} market for chemical, inorganic Cut-off, U	0.015	kg	Input
	Sodium nitrite {RER} market for sodium nitrite Cut-off, U	0.005	kg	Input
	Soda ash, dense {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.0001	kg	Input
	Nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} market for nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	0.0003	kg	Input
	Graphite {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.012	kg	Input
	Paraffin {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.057	kg	Input
	Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether {RER} market for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Butyldiglycol acetate {GLO} market for butyldiglycol acetate Cut-off, U	0.0004	kg	Input
	Lactic acid {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.0002	kg	Input
	Phosphoric acid, industrial grade, without water, in 85% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.00005	kg	Input
	Polydimethylsiloxane {GLO} market for polydimethylsiloxane Cut-off, U	0.00001	kg	Input
	Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether {RER} market for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether Cut-off, U	0.0003	kg	Input
	Triethylene glycol {RER} market for triethylene glycol Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input

	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0.0003	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.007	kWh	Input
painting (top coat)	Alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state {RER} market for alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state Cut-off, U	0.038	kg	Input
	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.074	m3	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	kWh	Input
Natural gas	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.173	m3	Input
Compressed air	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	4.200	m3	Input
Water	Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	0.011	m3	Input
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.120	kg	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.013	kg	Input
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.005	kg	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.007	tkm	Input
Wastes	Disposal, inert material, 0% water, to sanitary landfill/CH U	0.013	kg	Output
	Hazardous waste, for underground deposit {RER} market for hazardous waste, for underground deposit Cut-off, U	0.004	kg	Output
	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of scrap steel, inert material landfill Cut-off, U	0.031	kg	Output
	Wastewater	0.002	m3	Output

Table 11. LCI Fatigue4Light Wheel

F4L WHEEL		8.91 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Rim line	CP800	4.75	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.630	kWh	Input
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	0.620	m3	Input
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	4.750	tkm	Input
Disc line	CP800	6.240	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.360	kWh	Input
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	0.280	m3	Input
	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	2.080	kg	Output
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	6.240	tkm	Input
Welding	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.031	kg	Input
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	0.024	kg	Input
	Carbon dioxide, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.005	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.003	tkm	Input
Flowforming	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.68	kWh	Input
Assembly	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.635	kWh	Input
Sandblasting	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.012	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.4	kWh	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	tkm	Input
Cataphoresys process	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.010	kg	Input
	Non-ionic surfactant {GLO} market for non-ionic surfactant Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Sulfuric acid {RER} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Chemical, inorganic {GLO} market for chemical, inorganic Cut-off, U	0.015	kg	Input
	Sodium nitrite {RER} market for sodium nitrite Cut-off, U	0.005	kg	Input

	Soda ash, dense {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.0001	kg	Input
	Nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} market for nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	0.0003	kg	Input
	Graphite {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.012	kg	Input
	Paraffin {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.057	kg	Input
	Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether {RER} market for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Butyldiglycol acetate {GLO} market for butyldiglycol acetate Cut-off, U	0.0004	kg	Input
	Lactic acid {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.0002	kg	Input
	Phosphoric acid, industrial grade, without water, in 85% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.00005	kg	Input
	Polydimethylsiloxane {GLO} market for polydimethylsiloxane Cut-off, U	0.00001	kg	Input
	Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether {RER} market for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether Cut-off, U	0.0003	kg	Input
	Triethylene glycol {RER} market for triethylene glycol Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0.0003	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.007	tkm	Input
painting (top coat)	Alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state {RER} market for alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state Cut-off, U	0.038	kg	Input
	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.074	m3	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	tkm	Input
Natural gas	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.173	m3	Input
Compressed air	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	4.200	m3	Input
Water	Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	0.011	m3	Input
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.120	kg	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.013	kg	Input
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.005	kg	Input
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.007	tkm	Input
Wastes	Disposal, inert material, 0% water, to sanitary landfill/CH U	0.013	kg	Output
	Hazardous waste, for underground deposit {RER} market for hazardous waste, for underground deposit Cut-off, U	0.004	kg	Output
	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of scrap steel, inert material landfill Cut-off, U	0.031	kg	Output
	Wastewater	0.002	m3	Output

Lab-demonstrators for materials evaluated in D1.4 were prepared and are presented in Table 12 and Table 13 for hot and cold forming respectively. And Table 14 presents the hybrid solution Lab-demonstrator.

Table 12. LCI hot formed Lab-demonstrators

L-shape conventional hot formed 22MnB5		1.08 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	22MnB5	1.09	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Furnace	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	70.0	kWh	Input
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Laser cutting machine	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	4.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.011	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.546	tkm	Input

L-shape F4L hot formed AISI 410S
0.726 kg

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	AISI 410S	0.73	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Furnace	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	70.0	kWh	Input
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Laser cutting machine	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	4.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Scrap steel (Europe without Switzerland) market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.007	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 (RER) market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.056	tkm	Input

Table 13. LCI cold formed Lab-demonstrators
L-shape conventional cold formed DP600
0.796 kg

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	DP600	0.80	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Scrap steel (Europe without Switzerland) market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.008	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 (RER) market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.188	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship (GLO) transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.535	tkm	Input

L-shape F4L cold formed CP800
0.636 kg

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	CP800	0.64	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Scrap steel (Europe without Switzerland) market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.006	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 (RER) market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.321	tkm	Input

L-shape F4L cold formed CP980
0.654 kg

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	CP980	0.66	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Scrap steel (Europe without Switzerland) market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.007	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 (RER) market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.331	tkm	Input

L-shape F4L cold formed S355MC
0.671 kg

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	S355MC	0.68	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage (ES) market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input

Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.007	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.339	tkm	Input
L-shape F4L cold formed AA6181		0.128 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Materials	AA6181	0.13	kg	Input
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	17.0	kWh	Input
Waste	Aluminium scrap, new {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.001	kg	Output
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.064	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.168	tkm	Input

Table 14. LCI Fatigue4Light L-shape hybrid

L-shape F4L hybrid		0.100 kg		
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	INPUT/OUTPUT
Al cut and bending	AA6181	2.39	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.08	kWh	Input
	Aluminium (waste treatment) {GLO} recycling of aluminium Cut-off, U	2.290	kg	Output
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	4.343	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.808	tkm	Input
Al Wash	Soap {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	53	g	Input
	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0.150	kg	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.421	kWh	Input
	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of wastewater, average, capacity 1E9l/year Cut-off, U	0.000	m3	Output
Pre-preg	Glass fibre {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	170.0	g	Input
	Epoxy resin, liquid {RER} market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, U	250.0	g	Input
	Urea formaldehyde resin {RER} market for urea formaldehyde resin Cut-off, U	57.5	g	Input
	Ethylenediamine {RER} market for ethylenediamine Cut-off, U	12.5	g	Input
	Ethylenediamine {RER} market for ethylenediamine Cut-off, U	30.0	g	Input
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	20.0	g	Input
	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {RER} production Cut-off, U	50.0	g	Input
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	25.0	g	Input
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	20.0	g	Input
	Glued laminated timber, average glue mix {Europe without Switzerland} market for glued laminated timber, average glue mix Cut-off, U	10.0	g	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.18	kWh	Input
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, with energy recovery Cut-off, U	297.0	g	Output
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	0.279	tkm	Input
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.006	tkm	Input

	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.405	tkm	Input
Hybrid L-shape	Textile, nonwoven polyester {GLO} market for textile, nonwoven polyester Cut-off, U	4	g	Input
	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	50	g	Input
	Chemical, organic {GLO} fraction 1 from naphtha separation to generic market for Cut-off, U			
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	20	g	Input
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.34	kWh	Input
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {CH} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, with energy recovery Cut-off, U	448	g	Output

It is worth noting that for the hybrid L-shape demonstrator, the assumptions from Table 15 were made.

Table 15. L-shape assumptions

Assumptions L-Shape		Comment
2. AI cut	Electricity	equipment was too old, no information was found about the Watts - similar equipment was found at internet
4. AI Washing	Detergent	equipment is industrial (70 l total capacity) and the water is reused for others washings. The Unit is only 100 g (2 plates)
	Water	
	Electricity	
5. Prepreg	Electricity	equipment was too old, no information was found about the Watts - similar equipment was found at internet
6. L-shape	Electricity	equipment was too old, no information was found about the Watts - similar equipment was found at internet

4.2 LCI for LCC

For each category and life cycle stage, monetarized data is collected in an inventory. This data has been compiled from direct data obtained from partners and also from online resources when not provided.

Cost inventory for the conventional Lower Control Arm is presented in Table 16. Packaging was estimated based on the Wheel demonstrators inventory (materials for packaging) and the weight of the Lower Control Arm.

Costs of materials when not provided directly, were consulted on online markets. Transport price per ton-kilometer (tkm) were obtained from “The European Road Freight Rate Development Benchmark Q2 2022 | IRU | World Road Transport Organisation” n.d.

Table 16. Cost inventory Conventional Lower Control Arm

CONVENTIONAL LOWER CONTROL ARM		2.11kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		336500.00	EUR
Blanking	CP800	5.71	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.110	EUR

	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.780	EUR
Forming	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	0.135	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.265	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
Shot peening	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.093	EUR
Sleeve welding	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.012	EUR
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.397	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
Painting	Alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state {RER} market for alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state Cut-off, U	0.053	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.016	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
Annual maintenance		12.910	EUR
Labor		90.16	EUR

Table 17. Cost inventory Fatigue4Light Lower control arm

F4L LOWER CONTROL ARM		1.38 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		15200.00	EUR
Blanking	AA6181	2.390	EUR
	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0.656	EUR
	Sand {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.064	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.050	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	2.519	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.469	EUR
Al Wash	Soap {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	4.493	EUR
	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	2.362	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.012	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	0.224	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
Heat Treatment	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.187	EUR
Pre-preg	Glass fibre {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.169	EUR
	Epoxy resin, liquid {RER} market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, U	7.625	EUR
	Urea formaldehyde resin {RER} market for urea formaldehyde resin Cut-off, U	2.369	EUR
	Ethylenediamine {RER} market for ethylenediamine Cut-off, U	0.515	EUR
	Ethylenediamine {RER} market for ethylenediamine Cut-off, U	1.236	EUR
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	0.160	EUR
	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {RER} production Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.880	EUR
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1.074	EUR

	Glued laminated timber, average glue mix {Europe without Switzerland} market for glued laminated timber, average glue mix Cut-off, U	0.880	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.042	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	0.252	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	EUR
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.235	EUR
Hybrid LCA	Textile, nonwoven polyester {GLO} market for textile, nonwoven polyester Cut-off, U	0.011	EUR
	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	28.846	EUR
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	0.240	EUR
	Sealing tape, aluminium/PE, 50 mm wide {RER} production Cut-off, U	0.623	EUR
	Chemical, organic {GLO} fraction 1 from naphtha separation to generic market for Cut-off, U	23.000	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.468	EUR
LCA cut	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.030	EUR
Bonding	Epoxy resin, liquid {RER} market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, U	1.830	EUR
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	0.240	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.285	EUR
LCA B cut	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.099	EUR
Al parts	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.030	EUR
Labor		70.830	EUR

Cost inventory for Conventional and F4L Cross Beam Member are presented in Table 18 and Table 19. Packaging was estimated based on the Wheel demonstrators inventory (materials for packaging) and the weight of the Cross Beam Member. Initial investment has been estimated based on the L-shape demonstrators for the same materials, given that machinery can be considered similar between similar processing of the materials.

Table 18. Cost inventory Cross Beam Member - conventional

CONVENTIONAL CROSS BEAM MEMBER		18.9 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Blanking	S355MC steel	13	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.006	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	13.398	EUR
Stamping	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.026	EUR
Shot blasting	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.229	EUR
Laser	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.071	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.164	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.005	EUR
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.083	EUR
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.012	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
Labour		27	EUR

Table 19. Cost inventory Cross Beam Member Fatigue4Light

F4L CROSS BEAM MEMBER		12.6 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		250000.00	EUR

Blanking	22MnB5	8	EUR
	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.046	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.164	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	8.932	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
Furnace	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.700	EUR
Stamping	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.010	EUR
Shot blasting	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.230	EUR
Laser	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.031	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.105	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.055	EUR
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.008	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
Labour		61	EUR

Tables Table 20 and Table 21 present the cost inventory for the conventional and F4L Wheel. Initial investment has been estimated based on the L-shape demonstrators for the same materials, given that machinery can be considered similar between similar processing of the materials.

Table 20. Cost inventory conventional Wheel

CONVENTIONAL WHEEL		10 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Rim line	DP600	3	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.318	EUR
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	6.568	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	3.092	EUR
Disc line	DP600	3.374	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.182	EUR
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	2.966	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	3.914	EUR
Welding	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.026	EUR
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Carbon dioxide, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
Flowforming Assembly	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.343	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.321	EUR
Sandblasting	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.010	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.185	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
Cataphoresys process	cataphoresys chemical	1.146	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	EUR
painting (top coat)	Alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state {RER} market for alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state Cut-off, U	0.167	EUR
	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.034	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
Natural gas	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.079	EUR

Compressed air	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	44.491	EUR
Water	Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	0.013	EUR
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	1.200	EUR
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.007	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	EUR
Labour		15.64	EUR

Table 21. Cost inventory Fatigue4Light Wheel

F4L WHEEL		8.91 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Rim line	CP800	2.38	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.318	EUR
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	6.568	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	2.755	EUR
Disc line	CP800	3.120	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.182	EUR
	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	2.966	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	3.619	EUR
Welding	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.026	EUR
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Carbon dioxide, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.002	EUR
Flowforming	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.343	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.321	EUR
Assembly	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.010	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.185	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
Cataphoresys process	cataphoresys chemical	1.146	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	EUR
painting (top coat)	Alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state {RER} market for alkyd paint, white, without water, in 60% solution state Cut-off, U	0.167	EUR
	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.034	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.001	EUR
Natural gas	Natural gas, high pressure {IT} market for Cut-off, U	0.079	EUR
Compressed air	Compressed air, 800 kPa gauge {RER} market for compressed air, 800 kPa gauge Cut-off, U	44.491	EUR
Water	Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	0.013	EUR
Packaging	EUR-flat pallet {RER} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	1.200	EUR
	Polyethylene, low density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Corrugated board box {RER} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.007	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	EUR
Labour		15.64	EUR

Table 22 presents the cost inventory for the hot formed Lab-demonstrators.

Table 22. Cost inventory hot-formed Lab-demonstrators

L-shape conventional hot formed 22MnB5		1.08 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		95300.00	EUR
Materials	22MnB5	0.60	EUR
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Furnace	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	26.3	EUR
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Laser cutting machine	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	1.5	EUR
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.317	EUR
Annual maintenance		340.000	EUR
Labour		30	EUR

L-shape F4L hot formed AISI 410S		0.726 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		95300.00	EUR
Materials	AISI 410S	1.34	EUR
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Furnace	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	26.3	EUR
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Laser cutting machine	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	1.5	EUR
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.032	EUR
Annual maintenance		340.000	EUR
Labour		30	EUR

Table 23 presents the cost inventory for the cold-formed Lab-demonstrators.

Table 23. Cost inventory Cold-formed Lab-demonstrators

L-shape conventional cold formed DP600		0.796 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Materials	DP600	0.40	EUR
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.109	EUR
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.310	EUR
Annual maintenance		398.000	EUR
Labour		30	EUR

L-shape F4L cold formed CP800 **0.636 kg**

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Materials	CP800	0.32	EUR
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	EUR
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.186	EUR
Annual maintenance		398.000	EUR
Labour		30	EUR

L-shape F4L cold formed CP980 **0.654 kg**

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Materials	CP980	0.56	kg
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	kWh
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	kWh
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	kWh
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.192	tkm
Annual maintenance		398.000	EUR
Labour		30	EUR

L-shape F4L cold formed S355MC **0.671 kg**

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	
Materials	S355MC	0.43	
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	
Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.197	
Annual maintenance		398.000	
Labour		30	EUR

L-shape F4L cold formed AA6181 **0.128 kg**

Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		78200.00	EUR
Materials	AA6181	0.0002	kg
Trimming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	kWh
Punching press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	kWh

Forming press/tool	Electricity, medium voltage {ES} market for Cut-off, U	6.4	kWh
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.037	tkm
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.097	tkm
Annual maintenance		398.000	EUR
Labour		30.000	EUR

Table 24 presents the cost inventory for the hybrid L-shape demonstrator.

Table 24. Cost inventory hybrid L-shape

L-shape F4L hybrid		0.188 kg	
Process Step	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Initial investment		15200.00	EUR
Al cut and bending	AA6181	4.493	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.019	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	2.519	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.469	EUR
Al Wash	Soap {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.468	EUR
	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	0.252	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.234	EUR
Pre-preg	Glass fibre {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.169	EUR
	Epoxy resin (Araldite® LY 1556)	7.625	EUR
	Hardener (Aradur® 1571)	2.369	EUR
	Accelerator paste (Accelerator 1573)	0.515	EUR
	Hardener based on polyamine (Hardener XB 3403)	1.236	EUR
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	0.160	EUR
	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {RER} production Cut-off, U	0.000	EUR
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.880	EUR
	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1.074	EUR
	Glued laminated timber, average glue mix {Europe without Switzerland} market for glued laminated timber, average glue mix Cut-off, U	0.880	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.042	EUR
	Transport, freight, rail/RER U	0.162	EUR
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	0.004	EUR
Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	0.235	EUR	
Hybrid L-shape	Textile, nonwoven polyester {GLO} market for textile, nonwoven polyester Cut-off, U	0.01	EUR
	Lubricating oil {RER} market for lubricating oil Cut-off, U	11.50	EUR
	Acetone	0.08	EUR
	Latex {RER} market for latex Cut-off, U	0.16	EUR
	Electricity, medium voltage {SE} market for Cut-off, U	0.42	EUR
Labour		50	EUR

Energy and fuel prices for the use phase of the demonstrator are considered as stated in Table 25 for each kilogram of demonstrator during its lifetime.

Table 25, Energy and fuel Europe average prices

Energy/Fuel prices	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)		
	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (mL/kg)	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (kWh/kg)	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle (mL/kg)
	20.09	6.03	3910.10	10.05	2792.93
Price € per unit	0.367	0.367	0.00164	0.367	0.00164
Price € per kg	7.374	2.212	6.413	3.687	4.580

5 LCA

5.1.1 LCA indicators

The impact of Fatigue4Light developed solutions on the environment will be evaluated and quantified using specific quantitative impact categories to provide comprehensive information on environmental assessment and its reduction.

In accordance with the mandatory elements stated in the ISO 14044:2006 standard, the selection of impact categories, category indicators and characterization models is mandatory for each and all LCA. For this study, selected impact assessment method is CML-IA (baseline, version 3.08) (Table 26). Developed by the Centre of Environmental Science (CML) at Leiden University in the Netherlands, this LCIA method was deemed most suitable for the study.

Table 26. Impact categories

Impact category	Units
Abiotic depletion (elements)	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq
Human toxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq
Acidification	kg SO2 eq
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq

5.1.2 LCA results

This section provides a summary of the evaluation and quantification of the environmental impacts of the demonstrators. The LCA was created using SimaPro software v 9.4.0.2, and the LCA assumptions and main considerations were made in accordance with the guidelines of the attributional LCA approach, as described in international standards ISO 14040:2006(ISO/TC 207

2006a) and 14044:2006(ISO/TC 207 2006b). The objective of this study is to assess the environmental burdens of Fatigue4Light solutions applied to demonstrator parts and evaluated in a BEV, HEV, and pHEV to determine their performance throughout the vehicle's lifetime. Results are presented according to the life cycle stages previously established in the goal and scope, providing an overview of the environmental performance from a general approach to each life cycle stage. Lower Control Arm results are presented in Table 27 and Table 28 for the Conventional CP800 solution and for the Hybrid solution correspondingly. For the Cross Beam Member, results are presented in Table 29 for the S355 solution and in Table 30 for the 22MnB5. Wheel LCA is presented in Table 31 for DP600 and in Table 32 for CP800. Lab-demonstrators results are presented in Table 33, Table 34, Table 35, Table 36, Table 37, Table 38, Table 39 and Table 40. Finally, the relative distribution of the Conventional and Fatigue4Light scenarios is presented.

Table 27. LCA Lower Control Arm – CP800

Lower Control Arm – Conventional

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	2.57E-04	2.34E-04	3.97E-03	2.90E-03	2.12E-06	4.93E-04	4.23E-03	3.16E-03
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	7.00E+02	1.09E+03	4.03E+03	3.19E+03	6.71E+00	1.80E+03	4.74E+03	3.90E+03
Global warming (GWP100a)	7.38E+01	9.68E+01	3.05E+02	2.45E+02	1.03E+00	1.72E+02	3.80E+02	3.20E+02
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	2.47E-06	4.18E-06	4.36E-05	3.23E-05	1.29E-07	6.79E-06	4.62E-05	3.49E-05
Human toxicity	4.35E+01	5.02E+01	3.31E+02	2.51E+02	2.56E-01	9.40E+01	3.75E+02	2.95E+02
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	3.60E+01	6.69E+01	2.54E+02	2.01E+02	1.91E+00	1.05E+02	2.92E+02	2.39E+02
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	7.90E+04	1.73E+05	2.97E+05	2.62E+05	1.10E+03	2.53E+05	3.77E+05	3.42E+05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	7.92E-02	2.94E-01	3.82E-01	3.57E-01	6.71E-04	3.74E-01	4.62E-01	4.37E-01
Photochemical oxidation	2.34E-02	1.83E-02	5.17E-02	4.21E-02	7.23E-05	4.18E-02	7.52E-02	6.56E-02
Acidification	2.71E-01	4.46E-01	1.21E+00	9.90E-01	1.83E-03	7.19E-01	1.48E+00	1.26E+00
Eutrophication	9.86E-02	3.33E-01	3.91E-01	3.75E-01	1.14E-03	4.33E-01	4.91E-01	4.74E-01

Table 28. LCA Lower Control Arm – Hybrid

Lower Control Arm – Hybrid

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	8.49E-05	2.56E-05	4.34E-04	3.18E-04	2.08E-07	1.11E-04	5.20E-04	4.03E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	1.55E+02	1.19E+02	4.42E+02	3.50E+02	4.80E-01	2.75E+02	5.97E+02	5.05E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	2.42E+01	1.06E+01	3.34E+01	2.69E+01	5.01E-01	3.53E+01	5.81E+01	5.16E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1.25E-06	4.58E-07	4.77E-06	3.54E-06	1.13E-08	1.72E-06	6.04E-06	4.80E-06
Human toxicity	1.08E+01	5.50E+00	3.63E+01	2.75E+01	1.33E-01	1.64E+01	4.72E+01	3.84E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	1.10E+01	7.33E+00	2.79E+01	2.20E+01	2.78E-01	1.86E+01	3.92E+01	3.33E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.89E+04	1.90E+04	3.26E+04	2.87E+04	2.98E+02	4.82E+04	6.18E+04	5.79E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	4.95E-01	3.22E-02	4.18E-02	3.91E-02	2.09E-04	5.28E-01	5.37E-01	5.35E-01
Photochemical oxidation	4.98E-03	2.00E-03	5.66E-03	4.61E-03	6.07E-06	6.99E-03	1.06E-02	9.60E-03
Acidification	5.72E-02	4.89E-02	1.32E-01	1.08E-01	1.76E-04	1.06E-01	1.90E-01	1.66E-01

Eutrophication	2.78E-02	3.65E-02	4.29E-02	4.10E-02	1.75E-04	6.44E-02	7.08E-02	6.90E-02
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Table 29. LCA Cross Beam Member – S355

Cross Beam Member – S355

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	2.26E-05	3.51E-04	5.95E-03	4.35E-03	6.83E-06	3.81E-04	5.98E-03	4.38E-03
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	5.14E+02	1.64E+03	6.05E+03	4.79E+03	3.99E+01	2.19E+03	6.60E+03	5.34E+03
Global warming (GWP100a)	5.88E+01	1.45E+02	4.57E+02	3.68E+02	2.83E+00	2.07E+02	5.19E+02	4.30E+02
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1.03E-06	6.28E-06	6.54E-05	4.85E-05	5.41E-07	7.85E-06	6.70E-05	5.01E-05
Human toxicity	1.38E+01	7.53E+01	4.96E+02	3.76E+02	1.41E+00	9.05E+01	5.12E+02	3.91E+02
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	2.08E+01	1.00E+02	3.82E+02	3.01E+02	2.21E+01	1.43E+02	4.25E+02	3.44E+02
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	3.74E+04	2.60E+05	4.46E+05	3.93E+05	7.81E+03	3.05E+05	4.91E+05	4.38E+05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	2.23E-02	4.41E-01	5.73E-01	5.35E-01	2.35E-03	4.66E-01	5.97E-01	5.60E-01
Photochemical oxidation	1.93E-02	2.74E-02	7.75E-02	6.32E-02	4.31E-04	4.72E-02	9.72E-02	8.29E-02
Acidification	1.91E-01	6.69E-01	1.81E+00	1.48E+00	1.08E-02	8.71E-01	2.01E+00	1.69E+00
Eutrophication	7.39E-02	4.99E-01	5.87E-01	5.62E-01	3.58E-03	5.77E-01	6.64E-01	6.39E-01

Table 30. LCA Cross Beam Member – 22MnB5

Cross Beam Member 22MnB5

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	1.64E-04	2.34E-04	3.97E-03	2.90E-03	3.65E-06	4.01E-04	4.13E-03	3.07E-03
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	4.06E+02	1.09E+03	4.03E+03	3.19E+03	1.92E+01	1.52E+03	4.46E+03	3.62E+03
Global warming (GWP100a)	4.52E+01	9.68E+01	3.05E+02	2.45E+02	1.57E+00	1.44E+02	3.52E+02	2.92E+02
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	9.33E-07	4.18E-06	4.36E-05	3.23E-05	2.75E-07	5.39E-06	4.48E-05	3.35E-05
Human toxicity	2.56E+01	5.02E+01	3.31E+02	2.51E+02	6.86E-01	7.65E+01	3.57E+02	2.77E+02
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	1.81E+01	6.69E+01	2.54E+02	2.01E+02	9.97E+00	9.50E+01	2.83E+02	2.29E+02
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	3.99E+04	1.73E+05	2.97E+05	2.62E+05	3.69E+03	2.17E+05	3.41E+05	3.06E+05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	4.05E-02	2.94E-01	3.82E-01	3.57E-01	1.23E-03	3.36E-01	4.23E-01	3.98E-01
Photochemical oxidation	1.44E-02	1.83E-02	5.17E-02	4.21E-02	2.08E-04	3.29E-02	6.63E-02	5.67E-02
Acidification	1.59E-01	4.46E-01	1.21E+00	9.90E-01	5.23E-03	6.10E-01	1.37E+00	1.15E+00
Eutrophication	6.09E-02	3.33E-01	3.91E-01	3.75E-01	1.93E-03	3.96E-01	4.54E-01	4.37E-01

Table 31. LCA wheel – DP600

Wheel – DP600

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	1.87E-04	1.86E-04	3.15E-03	2.30E-03	2.49E-06	3.75E-04	3.34E-03	2.49E-03
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	7.83E+02	8.66E+02	3.20E+03	2.53E+03	1.19E+01	1.66E+03	4.00E+03	3.33E+03
Global warming (GWP100a)	8.34E+01	7.68E+01	2.42E+02	1.95E+02	1.10E+00	1.61E+02	3.26E+02	2.79E+02
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	2.51E-06	3.32E-06	3.46E-05	2.57E-05	1.79E-07	6.01E-06	3.73E-05	2.84E-05
Human toxicity	4.21E+01	3.98E+01	2.63E+02	1.99E+02	4.30E-01	8.23E+01	3.05E+02	2.42E+02
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	4.93E+01	5.31E+01	2.02E+02	1.59E+02	5.76E+00	1.08E+02	2.57E+02	2.14E+02
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	1.66E+05	1.38E+05	2.36E+05	2.08E+05	2.24E+03	3.06E+05	4.04E+05	3.76E+05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1.23E-01	2.33E-01	3.03E-01	2.83E-01	8.28E-04	3.57E-01	4.27E-01	4.07E-01
Photochemical oxidation	2.89E-02	1.45E-02	4.10E-02	3.34E-02	1.29E-04	4.35E-02	7.00E-02	6.25E-02
Acidification	3.94E-01	3.54E-01	9.58E-01	7.85E-01	3.24E-03	7.51E-01	1.36E+00	1.18E+00
Eutrophication	1.13E-01	2.64E-01	3.11E-01	2.97E-01	1.32E-03	3.78E-01	4.25E-01	4.11E-01

Table 32. LCA wheel – CP800

Wheel – CP800

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	2.55E-04	1.66E-04	2.81E-03	2.05E-03	2.12E-06	4.23E-04	3.06E-03	2.31E-03
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	3.90E+02	7.71E+02	2.85E+03	2.26E+03	9.81E+00	1.17E+03	3.25E+03	2.66E+03
Global warming (GWP100a)	4.04E+01	6.85E+01	2.16E+02	1.74E+02	9.47E-01	1.10E+02	2.57E+02	2.15E+02
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1.34E-06	2.96E-06	3.08E-05	2.29E-05	1.50E-07	4.45E-06	3.23E-05	2.44E-05
Human toxicity	2.86E+01	3.55E+01	2.34E+02	1.77E+02	3.55E-01	6.45E+01	2.63E+02	2.06E+02
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	2.24E+01	4.73E+01	1.80E+02	1.42E+02	4.61E+00	7.43E+01	2.07E+02	1.69E+02
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	4.67E+04	1.23E+05	2.10E+05	1.85E+05	1.82E+03	1.71E+05	2.59E+05	2.34E+05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	5.68E-02	2.08E-01	2.70E-01	2.52E-01	7.02E-04	2.65E-01	3.27E-01	3.10E-01
Photochemical oxidation	1.34E-02	1.29E-02	3.65E-02	2.98E-02	1.06E-04	2.64E-02	5.00E-02	4.32E-02
Acidification	1.54E-01	3.16E-01	8.53E-01	7.00E-01	2.67E-03	4.72E-01	1.01E+00	8.56E-01
Eutrophication	5.71E-02	2.35E-01	2.77E-01	2.65E-01	1.13E-03	2.94E-01	3.35E-01	3.23E-01

Table 33. LCA L-shape DP600

L-shape – DP600

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	5.04E-05	1.48E-05	2.51E-04	1.83E-04	1.23E-07	6.54E-05	3.01E-04	2.34E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	2.33E+02	6.89E+01	2.55E+02	2.02E+02	3.36E-01	3.03E+02	4.89E+02	4.35E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	2.14E+01	6.12E+00	1.93E+01	1.55E+01	6.13E-02	2.76E+01	4.08E+01	3.70E+01

Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	9.84E-07	2.64E-07	2.75E-06	2.04E-06	7.14E-09	1.26E-06	3.75E-06	3.03E-06
Human toxicity	9.64E+00	3.17E+00	2.09E+01	1.58E+01	1.32E-02	1.28E+01	3.06E+01	2.55E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	1.01E+01	4.23E+00	1.61E+01	1.27E+01	6.42E-02	1.44E+01	2.62E+01	2.29E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	3.64E+04	1.10E+04	1.88E+04	1.65E+04	5.16E+01	4.74E+04	5.52E+04	5.30E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	6.08E-02	1.86E-02	2.41E-02	2.25E-02	3.85E-05	7.94E-02	8.49E-02	8.33E-02
Photochemical oxidation	6.12E-03	1.15E-03	3.26E-03	2.66E-03	3.62E-06	7.28E-03	9.39E-03	8.79E-03
Acidification	1.42E-01	2.82E-02	7.62E-02	6.25E-02	9.22E-05	1.70E-01	2.19E-01	2.05E-01
Eutrophication	3.33E-02	2.10E-02	2.47E-02	2.37E-02	6.67E-05	5.44E-02	5.81E-02	5.71E-02

Table 34. LCA L-shape S355

L-shape – S355

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	4.72E-05	1.25E-05	2.11E-04	1.55E-04	1.03E-07	5.97E-05	2.59E-04	2.02E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	2.02E+02	5.81E+01	2.15E+02	1.70E+02	2.77E-01	2.60E+02	4.17E+02	3.72E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	1.80E+01	5.16E+00	1.62E+01	1.31E+01	5.14E-02	2.32E+01	3.43E+01	3.11E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	8.84E-07	2.23E-07	2.32E-06	1.72E-06	5.94E-09	1.11E-06	3.21E-06	2.61E-06
Human toxicity	7.68E+00	2.67E+00	1.76E+01	1.34E+01	1.09E-02	1.04E+01	2.53E+01	2.10E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	7.77E+00	3.56E+00	1.36E+01	1.07E+01	4.97E-02	1.14E+01	2.14E+01	1.85E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.69E+04	9.24E+03	1.58E+04	1.40E+04	4.21E+01	3.62E+04	4.28E+04	4.09E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	5.49E-02	1.57E-02	2.03E-02	1.90E-02	3.21E-05	7.06E-02	7.52E-02	7.39E-02
Photochemical oxidation	4.90E-03	9.74E-04	2.75E-03	2.24E-03	2.98E-06	5.88E-03	7.66E-03	7.15E-03
Acidification	1.23E-01	2.38E-02	6.43E-02	5.27E-02	7.59E-05	1.47E-01	1.88E-01	1.76E-01
Eutrophication	2.86E-02	1.77E-02	2.08E-02	2.00E-02	5.58E-05	4.64E-02	4.95E-02	4.86E-02

Table 35. LCA L-shape CP800

L-shape – CP800

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	4.68E-05	1.18E-05	2.00E-04	1.46E-04	9.76E-08	5.87E-05	2.47E-04	1.93E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	2.01E+02	5.50E+01	2.03E+02	1.61E+02	2.60E-01	2.56E+02	4.05E+02	3.62E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	1.79E+01	4.88E+00	1.54E+01	1.24E+01	4.86E-02	2.29E+01	3.34E+01	3.04E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	8.77E-07	2.11E-07	2.20E-06	1.63E-06	5.61E-09	1.09E-06	3.08E-06	2.51E-06
Human toxicity	7.49E+00	2.53E+00	1.67E+01	1.26E+01	1.02E-02	1.00E+01	2.42E+01	2.01E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	7.44E+00	3.38E+00	1.28E+01	1.01E+01	4.58E-02	1.09E+01	2.03E+01	1.76E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.66E+04	8.75E+03	1.50E+04	1.32E+04	3.95E+01	3.54E+04	4.16E+04	3.98E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	5.47E-02	1.48E-02	1.93E-02	1.80E-02	3.03E-05	6.96E-02	7.40E-02	7.28E-02
Photochemical oxidation	4.87E-03	9.22E-04	2.61E-03	2.13E-03	2.80E-06	5.79E-03	7.48E-03	6.99E-03
Acidification	1.23E-01	2.25E-02	6.09E-02	4.99E-02	7.13E-05	1.45E-01	1.84E-01	1.73E-01
Eutrophication	2.84E-02	1.68E-02	1.97E-02	1.89E-02	5.27E-05	4.53E-02	4.82E-02	4.74E-02

Table 36. LCA L-shape CP980

L-shape – CP980

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	4.68E-05	1.22E-05	2.06E-04	1.51E-04	1.01E-07	5.90E-05	2.53E-04	1.98E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	2.01E+02	5.66E+01	2.09E+02	1.66E+02	2.69E-01	2.58E+02	4.11E+02	3.67E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	1.79E+01	5.03E+00	1.58E+01	1.27E+01	5.01E-02	2.30E+01	3.38E+01	3.07E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	8.77E-07	2.17E-07	2.26E-06	1.68E-06	5.78E-09	1.10E-06	3.15E-06	2.56E-06
Human toxicity	7.49E+00	2.61E+00	1.72E+01	1.30E+01	1.05E-02	1.01E+01	2.47E+01	2.05E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	7.44E+00	3.48E+00	1.32E+01	1.04E+01	4.78E-02	1.10E+01	2.07E+01	1.79E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.66E+04	9.00E+03	1.54E+04	1.36E+04	4.09E+01	3.56E+04	4.21E+04	4.02E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	5.47E-02	1.53E-02	1.98E-02	1.85E-02	3.13E-05	7.00E-02	7.46E-02	7.33E-02
Photochemical oxidation	4.87E-03	9.50E-04	2.68E-03	2.19E-03	2.89E-06	5.82E-03	7.55E-03	7.06E-03
Acidification	1.23E-01	2.32E-02	6.27E-02	5.14E-02	7.37E-05	1.46E-01	1.86E-01	1.74E-01
Eutrophication	2.84E-02	1.73E-02	2.03E-02	1.95E-02	5.44E-05	4.58E-02	4.88E-02	4.79E-02

Table 37. LCA L-shape AA6181

L-shape – AA6181

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	4.76E-05	2.37E-06	4.02E-05	2.94E-05	1.97E-08	5.00E-05	8.78E-05	7.70E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	1.89E+02	1.11E+01	4.09E+01	3.24E+01	5.33E-02	2.00E+02	2.30E+02	2.21E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	1.64E+01	9.81E-01	3.09E+00	2.49E+00	9.81E-03	1.74E+01	1.95E+01	1.89E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	8.68E-07	4.24E-08	4.42E-07	3.28E-07	1.14E-09	9.12E-07	1.31E-06	1.20E-06
Human toxicity	7.56E+00	5.09E-01	3.35E+00	2.54E+00	2.09E-03	8.07E+00	1.09E+01	1.01E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	7.46E+00	6.78E-01	2.58E+00	2.04E+00	9.88E-03	8.15E+00	1.00E+01	9.50E+00
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.70E+04	1.76E+03	3.01E+03	2.66E+03	8.15E+00	2.88E+04	3.01E+04	2.97E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	5.51E-02	2.98E-03	3.87E-03	3.62E-03	6.14E-06	5.81E-02	5.90E-02	5.88E-02
Photochemical oxidation	4.45E-03	1.85E-04	5.24E-04	4.27E-04	5.74E-07	4.64E-03	4.98E-03	4.88E-03
Acidification	1.19E-01	4.52E-03	1.22E-02	1.00E-02	1.46E-05	1.24E-01	1.31E-01	1.29E-01
Eutrophication	2.70E-02	3.37E-03	3.97E-03	3.80E-03	1.07E-05	3.03E-02	3.09E-02	3.08E-02

Table 38. LCA L-shape AISI 410

L-shape – AISI 410

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	1.61E-04	1.36E-05	2.30E-04	1.68E-04	1.13E-07	1.74E-04	3.90E-04	3.29E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	4.35E+02	6.32E+01	2.34E+02	1.85E+02	3.05E-01	4.99E+02	6.69E+02	6.20E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	3.84E+01	5.61E+00	1.77E+01	1.42E+01	5.61E-02	4.41E+01	5.61E+01	5.27E+01

Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1.94E-06	2.42E-07	2.53E-06	1.87E-06	6.51E-09	2.19E-06	4.47E-06	3.82E-06
Human toxicity	2.46E+01	2.91E+00	1.92E+01	1.45E+01	1.19E-02	2.75E+01	4.38E+01	3.91E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	1.71E+01	3.88E+00	1.47E+01	1.16E+01	5.65E-02	2.10E+01	3.19E+01	2.88E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	5.99E+04	1.00E+04	1.72E+04	1.52E+04	4.66E+01	7.00E+04	7.72E+04	7.52E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1.27E-01	1.70E-02	2.21E-02	2.07E-02	3.51E-05	1.44E-01	1.49E-01	1.48E-01
Photochemical oxidation	1.03E-02	1.06E-03	2.99E-03	2.44E-03	3.28E-06	1.13E-02	1.33E-02	1.27E-02
Acidification	2.67E-01	2.59E-02	6.99E-02	5.73E-02	8.36E-05	2.93E-01	3.37E-01	3.24E-01
Eutrophication	6.18E-02	1.93E-02	2.27E-02	2.17E-02	6.10E-05	8.12E-02	8.46E-02	8.36E-02

Table 39. LCA L-shape 22MnB5

L-shape – 22MnB5

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	1.11E-04	2.01E-05	3.40E-04	2.49E-04	1.71E-07	1.31E-04	4.51E-04	3.59E-04
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	4.23E+02	9.35E+01	3.46E+02	2.74E+02	4.83E-01	5.17E+02	7.69E+02	6.97E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	3.76E+01	8.30E+00	2.61E+01	2.10E+01	8.43E-02	4.60E+01	6.38E+01	5.87E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1.87E-06	3.59E-07	3.74E-06	2.77E-06	1.00E-08	2.24E-06	5.62E-06	4.65E-06
Human toxicity	1.73E+01	4.30E+00	2.84E+01	2.15E+01	1.88E-02	2.16E+01	4.57E+01	3.88E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	1.64E+01	5.74E+00	2.18E+01	1.72E+01	1.04E-01	2.23E+01	3.83E+01	3.37E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	5.76E+04	1.49E+04	2.55E+04	2.25E+04	7.56E+01	7.25E+04	8.31E+04	8.01E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1.18E-01	2.52E-02	3.27E-02	3.06E-02	5.34E-05	1.43E-01	1.50E-01	1.48E-01
Photochemical oxidation	1.02E-02	1.57E-03	4.43E-03	3.61E-03	5.20E-06	1.17E-02	1.46E-02	1.38E-02
Acidification	2.60E-01	3.82E-02	1.03E-01	8.48E-02	1.32E-04	2.98E-01	3.64E-01	3.45E-01
Eutrophication	6.02E-02	2.85E-02	3.35E-02	3.21E-02	9.22E-05	8.88E-02	9.38E-02	9.24E-02

Table 40. LCA L-shape hybrid

L-shape – Hybrid

Impact category	Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage pHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	pHEV
Abiotic depletion	5.91E-05	3.29E-06	5.57E-05	4.07E-05	2.84E-08	6.24E-05	1.15E-04	9.98E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	1.28E+02	1.53E+01	5.67E+01	4.48E+01	5.83E-02	1.43E+02	1.84E+02	1.73E+02
Global warming (GWP100a)	1.92E+01	1.36E+00	4.28E+00	3.45E+00	1.83E-01	2.07E+01	2.36E+01	2.28E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1.04E-06	5.88E-08	6.12E-07	4.54E-07	1.46E-09	1.10E-06	1.65E-06	1.49E-06
Human toxicity	8.49E+00	7.05E-01	4.65E+00	3.52E+00	5.07E-02	9.25E+00	1.32E+01	1.21E+01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	8.55E+00	9.40E-01	3.58E+00	2.82E+00	1.03E-01	9.59E+00	1.22E+01	1.15E+01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.54E+04	2.44E+03	4.18E+03	3.68E+03	1.06E+02	2.79E+04	2.97E+04	2.92E+04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	2.40E-01	4.13E-03	5.36E-03	5.01E-03	7.06E-05	2.44E-01	2.45E-01	2.45E-01
Photochemical oxidation	4.02E-03	2.57E-04	7.26E-04	5.92E-04	1.01E-06	4.27E-03	4.74E-03	4.61E-03
Acidification	4.82E-02	6.27E-03	1.70E-02	1.39E-02	3.47E-05	5.45E-02	6.52E-02	6.22E-02
Eutrophication	2.09E-02	4.68E-03	5.50E-03	5.26E-03	4.19E-05	2.57E-02	2.65E-02	2.63E-02

After presenting all the results, Global Warming Potential and BEV options will be used to depict a comparison of all different demonstrators. Figure 4 depicts the comparison for the two solutions for the Lower Control Arm. the Hybrid solution presents evidently lower environmental impact. Manufacturing and assembly stage already shows lower impact, but also the reduced weight and energy consumption during the use stage provide a reduction of around 90% of the stage impact and in total an 86% lower impact.

Figure 4. GWP Lower Control Arm comparison

Cross Beam Member solutions GWP results are presented in Figure 5. 22MnB5 solution presents lower environmental impact. Weight reduction between demonstrators is around 30% while GWP shows around 23% lower impact.

Figure 5. GWP Cross Beam Member comparison

Figure 6 presents the Wheel results for both solutions DP600 and CP800. With around 50% weight reduction, GWP is lower for CP800 lighter solution in 32% including all life cycle stages. Major reduction is seen in the material production as shown in D1.4.

Figure 6. GWP Wheel comparison

Figure 7 depicts Lab-demonstrator solutions GWP. Even though S355, CP800, CP980 and AA6181 have similar GWP impact during the manufacturing and assembly stage, use stage shows the real difference when considering the weight reduction and therefore energy consumption reduction, displaying a clear difference in favor of AA6181 solution when comparing hot formed solutions. On the other hand, cold formed solutions present similar results within these two solutions, it differs proportionally in the use stage due to energy consumption differences (weight). Lowest GWP is shown by AA6181, followed by the Hybrid solution.

Figure 7. GWP L-shape comparison

End-of-Life stage presents a low relevance when compared to the manufacturing and use stages in all demonstrators.

6 LCC

Life cycle costing study includes all costs of manufacturing and energy and fuel needed during the use phase. All costs are related to the demonstrator, and not the entire vehicle. Fuel and energy consumption during the use phase are calculated in relation to the weight of the demonstrator for the different types of EV (BEV, HEV, and pHEV).

Table 41 presents a summary of the manufacturing cost of each of the demonstrators, including the cost of investment and maintenance. Although maintenance has only been included in the cases where direct data was available.

Use phase costs, related to energy and fuel consumption are presented in Table 42 for each of the three different options of EV. Table presents the cost in € per demonstrator in its lifetime in BEV, HEV and pHEV vehicles.

Table 41. LCC summary for all demonstrators' manufacturing

Cost Categories	Lower Control Arm – CP800	Lower Control Arm - Hybrid	CBM_Cold Stamped	CBM_Press Hardened	Wheel CP800	Wheel DP600	L-Shape 22MnB5	L-Shape AISI 410S	L-Shape DP600	L-Shape S355MC	L-Shape CP800	L-Shape CP980	L-Shape AA6181	L-Shape Hybrid
CAPEX	22.43	1.01	5.21	16.67	5.21	5.21	6.35	6.35	5.21	5.21	5.21	5.21	5.21	1.01
Investment	22.43	1.01	5.21	16.67	5.21	5.21	6.35	6.35	5.21	5.21	5.21	5.21	5.21	1.01
Indirect Cost	12.91	-	-	-	-	-	0.34	0.34	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	-
Maintenance	12.91	-	-	-	-	-	0.34	0.34	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	-
Direct Cost	97.80	219.92	54.35	78.91	34.22	33.10	71.52	71.98	50.00	49.80	49.68	49.93	49.31	85.69
Labour	90.16	70.83	27.00	61.00	15.64	15.64	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	50.00
Material	5.94	77.51	13.52	7.77	7.01	8.88	0.60	1.34	0.40	0.43	0.32	0.56	0.00	31.38
Utilities	-	3.44	-	-	0.01	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.25
Electricity	0.92	64.43	0.43	1.21	1.55	1.55	40.61	40.61	19.18	19.18	19.18	19.18	19.18	0.66
Transport	0.78	3.70	13.40	8.94	10.00	7.02	0.32	0.03	0.42	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.13	3.39
TOTAL	133.15	220.93	59.56	95.58	39.43	38.31	78.21	78.68	55.61	55.42	55.29	55.54	54.92	86.70

Table 42. Use phase fuel/energy cost per VE (€/demonstrator)

Demonstrator	Weight	BEV	HEV (30%) /electricity	fuel	PHEV (50%) electricity	fuel
Lower Control Arm - Conventional	12.600	92.914	27.874	80.798	46.457	57.713
Lower Control Arm - Hybrid	1.380	10.176	3.053	8.849	5.088	6.321
CBM_Cold Stamped	18.900	139.371	41.811	121.198	69.686	86.570
CBM_Press Hardened	12.600	92.914	27.874	80.798	46.457	57.713
Wheel_DP600	10.000	73.741	22.122	64.126	36.871	45.804
Wheel_CP800	8.910	65.704	19.711	57.136	32.852	40.811
L-Shape 22MnB5	1.080	7.964	2.389	6.926	3.982	4.947
L-Shape AISI 410S	0.730	5.383	1.615	4.681	2.692	3.344
L-Shape DP600	0.796	5.870	1.761	5.104	2.935	3.646
L-Shape S355MC	0.671	4.950	1.485	4.304	2.475	3.074
L-Shape CP800	0.636	4.687	1.406	4.076	2.343	2.911
L-Shape CP980	0.654	4.826	1.448	4.196	2.413	2.997
L-Shape AA6181	0.128	0.942	0.283	0.819	0.471	0.585
L-Shape Hybrid	0.177	1.305	0.392	1.135	0.653	0.811

Results for Lower Control Arm are presented in Table 43 and Table 44 for Conventional and Hybrid demonstrators respectively, for BEV, HEV and PHEV configurations

Table 43. LCC Conventional Lower Control Arm

Lower Control Arm – Conventional			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	22.43	22.43	22.43
Investment	22.43	22.43	22.43
Indirect Cost	12.91	12.91	12.91
Maintenance	12.91	12.91	12.91
Direct Cost	97.80	97.80	97.80
Labor	90.16	90.16	90.16
Material	5.94	5.94	5.94
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	0.92	0.92	0.92
Transport	0.78	0.78	0.78
Use cost	92.91	108.67	104.17
Use phase electricity	92.91	27.87	46.46
Use phase fuel		80.80	57.71
TOTAL	226.06	241.82	237.32

Table 44. LCC Hybrid Lower Control Arm

Lower Control Arm – Hybrid			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	1.01	1.01	1.01
Investment	1.01	1.01	1.01
Indirect Cost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maintenance	0.00	0.00	0.00
Direct Cost	219.92	219.92	219.92
Labor	70.83	70.83	70.83
Material	77.51	77.51	77.51
Utilities	3.44	3.44	3.44
Electricity	64.43	64.43	64.43
Transport	3.70	3.70	3.70
Use cost	10.18	11.90	11.41
Use phase electricity	10.18	3.05	5.09
Use phase fuel		8.85	6.32
TOTAL	231.11	232.83	232.34

Results from both LCA demonstrators are not so different in total, but in the breakdown the higher costs distribution is clearly different. Major costs from the conventional solution comes from Direct cost, more specifically from labor cost, and also from use energy/fuel consumption. While for the hybrid demonstrator cost is evidently coming from Direct cost, distributed in materials, labor and electricity for production, and the use phase is one of the smallest items.

Results for Cross Beam Member are presented in Table 45 and Table 46 for cold stamped and press hardened demonstrators respectively, for BEV, HEV and pHEV configurations.

Table 45. LCC Cross Beam Member - Cold stamped

CBM – Cold Stamped			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maintenance	0.00	0.00	0.00
Direct Cost	54.35	54.35	54.35
Labor	27.00	27.00	27.00
Material	13.52	13.52	13.52
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	0.43	0.43	0.43
Transport	13.40	13.40	13.40
Use cost	139.37	163.01	156.26
Use phase electricity	139.37	41.81	69.69
Use phase fuel		121.20	86.57
TOTAL	198.94	222.57	215.82

Table 46. LCC Cross Beam Member - Press hardened

CBM – Press Hardened			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	16.67	16.67	16.67
Investment	16.67	16.67	16.67
Indirect Cost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maintenance	0.00	0.00	0.00
Direct Cost	78.91	78.91	78.91
Labor	61.00	61.00	61.00
Material	7.77	7.77	7.77
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	1.21	1.21	1.21
Transport	8.94	8.94	8.94
Use cost	92.91	108.67	104.17
Use phase electricity	92.91	27.87	46.46
Use phase fuel		80.80	57.71
TOTAL	188.49	204.25	199.75

Both CBM demonstrators have similar results of around 200€ per demonstrator, with the highest cost coming from the use phase for both.

Results for Wheel demonstrators are presented in Table 47 and Table 48 for DP600 and CP800 respectively, for BEV, HEV and pHEV configurations

Table 47. LCC DP600 Wheel

Wheel – DP600			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maintenance	0.00	0.00	0.00
Direct Cost	34.22	34.22	34.22
Labor	15.64	15.64	15.64
Material	7.01	7.01	7.01
Utilities	0.01	0.01	0.01
Electricity	1.55	1.55	1.55
Transport	10.00	10.00	10.00
Use cost	73.74	86.25	82.67
Use phase electricity	73.74	22.12	36.87
Use phase fuel		64.13	45.80
TOTAL	113.18	125.68	122.11

Table 48. LCC CP800 Wheel

Wheel – CP800			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maintenance	0.00	0.00	0.00
Direct Cost	33.10	33.10	33.10

Labor	15.64	15.64	15.64
Material	8.88	8.88	8.88
Utilities	0.01	0.01	0.01
Electricity	1.55	1.55	1.55
Transport	7.02	7.02	7.02
Use cost	65.70	76.85	73.66
Use phase electricity	65.70	19.71	32.85
Use phase fuel		57.14	40.81
TOTAL	104.02	115.16	111.98

Wheel demonstrators have almost the same cost except for a slight difference in the use phase due to the difference in weight of the demonstrator and therefore energy/fuel consumption.

Table 49 and Table 50 present LCC for hot formed L-shape demonstrators.

Table 49. LCC L-shape 22MnB5

L-Shape – 22MnB5

Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	6.35	6.35	6.35
Investment	6.35	6.35	6.35
Indirect Cost	0.34	0.34	0.34
Maintenance	0.34	0.34	0.34
Direct Cost	71.52	71.52	71.52
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	0.60	0.60	0.60
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	40.61	40.61	40.61
Transport	0.32	0.32	0.32
Use cost	7.96	9.31	8.93
Use phase electricity	7.96	2.39	3.98
Use phase fuel		6.93	4.95
TOTAL	86.18	87.53	87.14

Table 50. LCC L-shape AISI 410S

L-Shape – AISI 410S

Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	6.35	6.35	6.35
Investment	6.35	6.35	6.35
Indirect Cost	0.34	0.34	0.34
Maintenance	0.34	0.34	0.34
Direct Cost	71.98	71.98	71.98
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	1.34	1.34	1.34
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	40.61	40.61	40.61
Transport	0.03	0.03	0.03
Use cost	5.38	6.30	6.04
Use phase electricity	5.38	1.61	2.69

Use phase fuel		4.68	3.34
TOTAL	84.06	84.97	84.71

Hot formed L-shape demonstrators sum up for almost the same cost and it is mainly due to Direct Costs, more specifically Labor and Electricity consumption for the manufacturing process.

Cold stamped Lab-demonstrators results are presented in Table 51, Table 52, Table 53, Table 54 and Table 55.

Table 51. LCC L-shape DP600

L-Shape – DP600

Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.40	0.40	0.40
Maintenance	0.40	0.40	0.40
Direct Cost	50.00	50.00	50.00
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	0.40	0.40	0.40
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	19.18	19.18	19.18
Transport	0.42	0.42	0.42
Use cost	5.87	6.87	6.58
Use phase electricity	5.87	1.76	2.93
Use phase fuel		5.10	3.65
TOTAL	61.48	62.47	62.19

Table 52. LCC L-shape S355MC

L-Shape – S355MC

Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.40	0.40	0.40
Maintenance	0.40	0.40	0.40
Direct Cost	49.80	49.80	49.80
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	0.43	0.43	0.43
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	19.18	19.18	19.18
Transport	0.20	0.20	0.20
Use cost	4.95	5.79	5.55
Use phase electricity	4.95	1.48	2.47
Use phase fuel		4.30	3.07
TOTAL	60.36	61.20	60.96

Table 53. LCC L-shape CP800

L-Shape – CP800			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.40	0.40	0.40
Maintenance	0.40	0.40	0.40
Direct Cost	49.68	49.68	49.68
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	0.32	0.32	0.32
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	19.18	19.18	19.18
Transport	0.19	0.19	0.19
Use cost	4.69	5.48	5.25
Use phase electricity	4.69	1.41	2.34
Use phase fuel		4.08	2.91
TOTAL	59.98	60.78	60.55

Table 54. LCC L-shape CP980

L-Shape – CP980			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.40	0.40	0.40
Maintenance	0.40	0.40	0.40
Direct Cost	49.93	49.93	49.93
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	0.56	0.56	0.56
Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	19.18	19.18	19.18
Transport	0.19	0.19	0.19
Use cost	4.83	5.64	5.41
Use phase electricity	4.83	1.45	2.41
Use phase fuel		4.20	3.00
TOTAL	60.37	61.18	60.95

Table 55. LCC L-shape AA6181

L-Shape – AA6181			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	5.21	5.21	5.21
Investment	5.21	5.21	5.21
Indirect Cost	0.40	0.40	0.40
Maintenance	0.40	0.40	0.40
Direct Cost	49.31	49.31	49.31
Labor	30.00	30.00	30.00
Material	0.00	0.00	0.00

Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	19.18	19.18	19.18
Transport	0.13	0.13	0.13
Use cost	0.94	1.10	1.06
Use phase electricity	0.94	0.28	0.47
Use phase fuel		0.82	0.58
TOTAL	55.86	56.02	55.98

LCC for cold stamped L-shape demonstrators are very similar to each other, although aluminium AA6181 does shows a slight difference in comparison with the rest. Major cost for AA6181 comes from Direct costs, mainly labor and electricity for manufacturing.

Results for the cost analysis of the hybrid L-shape demonstrator are presented in Table 56. Within the L-shape demonstrators, the hybrid option is the most expensive one due to labor and material costs.

Table 56. LCC hybrid L-shape

L-Shape – Hybrid			
Cost Categories	BEV	HEV (30%)	PHEV (50%)
CAPEX	1.01	1.01	1.01
Investment	1.01	1.01	1.01
Indirect Cost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maintenance	0.00	0.00	0.00
Direct Cost	85.69	85.69	85.69
Labor	50.00	50.00	50.00
Material	31.38	31.38	31.38
Utilities	0.25	0.25	0.25
Electricity	0.66	0.66	0.66
Transport	3.39	3.39	3.39
Use cost	1.31	1.53	1.46
Use phase electricity	1.31	0.39	0.65
Use phase fuel		1.14	0.81
TOTAL	88.01	88.23	88.16

As expected, when comparing BEV, HEV and pHEV configuration options, BEV is always the most cost efficient of the three, in second place would be pHEV and last HEV due to fuel consumption.

To conclude, from an economic perspective, regarding the Lower Control Arm, CP800 is a better option by 2% of the total cost. In the case of the Cross Beam Member, by 5% lower cost, the press hardened option is more viable. This difference is slightly higher in the case of the Wheel where CP800 is around 8% less expensive than DP600. Hot formed L-shape gives lower results, of around 2% less in AISI 410S. Moreover, cold shaped L-shape demonstrators show a slight difference for the aluminium alloy AA6181 of around 7% and the major difference comes from energy/fuel consumption during the use phase. Hybrid L-shape turned out to be, at least, 43% more expensive than all the other materials used in L-shape demonstrators.

It is worth noting that Transport cost has been estimated at the worst or highest economic cost. So even though, transport is not one of the highest cost, if a more efficient cost was considered, the overall economic cost wouldn't be significantly changed but the transport cost would be lower, probably in more than 50%.

7 Recyclability profiling

7.1 Induction heating as an option for GFRP's second life

7.1.1 Introduction

The worldwide concerns and demanding requirements for recycling, recovery, and reuse of end-of-life vehicles parts, to avoid waste of crucial materials and problems of disposal, has highly affected the automotive industry (Lu et al., 2014). Along the years, the use of lightweight materials such as polymer reinforced composites (i.e., glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP)) as substitutes or in combination with metals (i.e., aluminium and steel) in automotive vehicles have been intensified, reducing weight without compromising mechanical performance. However, the combination of diverse materials results in multiple raw material extraction, increase the number of production steps (directly related to energy consumption) as well as creates issues with the subsequent material separation (dismantling) and recycling (Brenea et al., 2017).

In this scenario, the use of technologies and processes for easy recycle and reuse of end-of-life sandwich structures, for instance aluminium faces and GFRP (epoxy matrix) core, are of great interest for industries. As for a sustainable society the energy efficiency and saving are key parameter, induction heating become a promising technology to separate sandwich structures parts for reuse and/or recycling purposes, since it has a high heating efficiency (electricity usage), no requirement for advanced cooling, and a higher geometrical flexibility (Rudnev et al., 2001).

Induction heating is the process of heating an electrically conducting object (i.e., aluminium face) by electromagnetic induction, where eddy currents are generated within the metallic material (Kardile et al., 2022). One of the main components of an induction heating system is the heating tip (induction coil). When the conductive sample is placed in the tip area, it is generated a well-defined heat pattern without any physical contact between the tip and the sample (see Figure 8.).

Figure 8. Scheme of the induction heating method

Despite the benefit with induction heating, conventional heating methods, which require large investment and low energy efficiency such as ovens or furnaces, powered by electricity or combustion of fossil fuels, are still dominant, due to technical limitations in existing induction heating technology (Frogner et al., 2011).

An efficient induction heating system will depend on different factors, such as the characteristics of the analysed material (i.e., the thickness and thermal properties), the design of the induction coil (which determines how effectively and efficiently a sample is heated), the capacity of the heating power, and the amount of temperature change required for the application. Furthermore, as induction heating requires that temperature cycling rate depends on the heat capacity of the material, controlling and measuring sample temperatures is difficult as it relies on pyrometry.

As mentioned, induction heating is a method of providing fast and consistent heat when properly set up, becoming a repeatable and controllable process. Moreover, it is a cost-effective heating method that can solve advanced heating problems, but drawbacks connected to existing induction

heating technology can be identified (Frogner et al., 2011), which prevents the technology to be fully exploited.

In Fatigue4Light project, induction heating method will be used to assess ease debonding of multi-material structure (sandwich aluminium/GFRP), being evaluated as a rapid energy efficient method to separate the composite core from the outer face. The remaining aluminium can be recycled through a "closed loop" process (state-of-the-art recycling methods), and the separated composite could be recycled, or reused as a part of a new sandwich material.

7.1.2 Method

For induction heating to become a controllable and repeatable process, it is necessary to make a proper set up for each type of material being analysed. Therefore, induction heating for Fatigue4Light sandwich flat samples, with 25 x 25 mm², is studied and developed on a laboratory scale at RISE, in the Laboratory testbeds (Mölnadal/Sweden). The examined material is a 3.5 mm thickness sandwich constituted by two EN AW-6082 T6 aluminium faces (0.8 mm thick each face) and GFRP core (\approx 1.9 mm thick). The used equipment is an Alesco A80 mobile induction unit (Figure 9a), with maximal system power of 3.7 kW (230 V, 15 kg, internal cooling). The output power of the unit can be adjusted in 5 steps.

For all induction heating samples, a medium output power is chosen (step 3, \approx 2.2 kW). The heating tip is a A80 standard tip from Alesco manufacturer with a 90 degree angle (Figure 9b). For temperature measurement, a pyrometer of type MAURER KTRD 4465-1 (Figure 9c) is used. Emissivity is chosen to 0.75, which was determined in other experiments for similar (anodized) aluminium plates. Temperature is measured close to the heated area. Real temperature of the material surface under the induction tip might therefore be higher. Due to the high heat conductivity of aluminium (170 W/m.K (MatWeb website)) and small sheet thickness (0.8 mm), it is assumed that the difference is neglectable.

Figure 9. a) Induction heating equipment; b) heating tips; and c) temperature measurement location (red arrow).

For the current method, the sample is positioned on a ceramic base, the heat is applied by placing a heating tip for flat surfaces (Figure 9) onto the aluminium face and manually moving the heating tip slowly over the surface. When the equipment power supply is switched on, the time to debonding of the aluminium/GFRP interface is started to measure (the heating time is manually controlled by pushing the release button). Thus, different debonding parameters, such as maximum temperature (T_{max}) and heating time (t), were evaluated.

The square specimens were heated to different temperatures levels, from 160-300 °C. Heating times and temperatures were: $t \approx 1$ s for $T_{max} \leq 160$ °C, and $t \approx 3$ s for $T_{max} = 300$ °C. After heating, the sample was inspected to assess whether the top face could be easily debonded from the core material, and the debonded surfaces (aluminium and core) were evaluated.

7.1.3 Results and discussion

The results are presented in Table 57. This gives an overview on the results achieved by manual heat treatment of aluminium/GFRP samples, using induction heating equipment.

Table 57. Induction-heated aluminium/GFRP samples with different debonding parameters.

T_{max} (°C)	t (s)	Comments	Debonded interface
160	1.0	No debonding, no signs of interface degradation, and no smoke.	-
200	1.5	No debonding, no signs of interface degradation, no smoke.	-
250#1	2	Moderate smoke generation, no browning of the interface, easy separation of the top sheet with a knife.	
250#2	2	Moderate smoke generation, some browning of the interface between Al and core, top sheet could be separated with a knife, some adhesion left	
250	2+5	Moderate smoke generation, easy separation of the top sheet, browning of the interface.	
270	2-3	Moderate to strong smoke generation, easy separation of the top sheet, stronger browning, and some blackening of the interface. Visible edge effects (black).	

300	3	Moderate to strong smoke generation, easy separation of top sheet by hand.	
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As observed in Table 57, for $T_{max} < 250\text{ °C}$ and $t < 2\text{ s}$, when the adopted induction heating method was used to lead to interfacial debonding, no satisfactory material separation was observed. Reasons were attributed to the ineffectiveness of direct induction heating due to satisfactory interfacial strength between aluminium and GFRP.

The best result was achieved for sample 250#1, heated at $T_{max} = 250\text{ °C}$ and $t = 2\text{ s}$, with moderate smoke generation, no degradation (browning) of the interface, and easy separation of the top aluminium sheet using a knife. Therefore, a second trial (250#2) was performed using the same debonding parameters. However, as for this study the method is manually performed, the heating tip is difficult to reproduce consistent result, especially when larger areas are to be treated (i.e., Figure 10).

For $T_{max} \geq 250\text{ °C}$ and $t > 2\text{ s}$, despite the aluminium/GFRP interface being easily debonded, no suitable results were obtained due to degradation (browning of the interface) of the GFRP. As the induction heating method is being used for debonding, the debonding temperature is considered as the temperature at which the thermal decomposition of the aluminium/GFRP interface occurs. Therefore, the interface debonding requires high temperatures, above the glass transition temperature ($T_g \approx 130\text{ °C}$) of the used epoxy matrix, which can overheat the components and even damage or destroy them. Furthermore, GFRP is a nonconductive material, thus, is being heated indirectly by first heating the conductive aluminium, which transfers heat to the nonconductive GFRP. However, aluminium is a nonferrous low-resistance metal and is difficult to heat (higher heat capacity), requiring larger currents to produce the same amount of heat.

A sample with larger area ($10.0 \times 2.5\text{ mm}^2$) was also heat treated by manually moving the heating tip slowly over the surface. Exact temperature measurement was not possible here due to method limitation. The interface after heating and separation of a larger sample are shown in Figure 10. Induction heating is in general critical at the edges as the electromagnetic field can concentrate there, leading to overheating of the sample edges and, with long heating times, even aluminium melting.

Figure 10. Debonding of aluminium/GFRP interface after induction heating of a larger area sample.

Analysing the debonded GFRP of the best (but not repeatable) achieved results (Figure 11), it is possible to observe many cracks and even delamination in the composite surface. This could be an indication that the reuse of such composite in a new sandwich material might not provide a

superior quality part, when compared with virgin sandwich properties. Moreover, reusing the recycled GFRP in another hybrid solution would require using an adhesive (i.e., epoxy-based) to bond the recycled GFRP with virgin aluminium faces. The necessity of using extra adhesive, with thickness dependent on the manufacturing parameters, is because GFRP cannot act as such due to its thermosetting nature (not possible to melt nor solidify).

Figure 11. Surface of the debonded GFRP, sample 250#1.

As the induction tests were performed on non-standardised dimension's specimens, the mechanical evaluation of the recycled GFRP/adhesive/virgin aluminium system was not performed. It is believed that the introduction of the adhesive (third material system) would result in different mechanical properties of the final material system, with different interface characteristics, thus, not comparable to the original hybrid solution.

Alternative solution

A conventional heating method was used as alternative to induction heating to debond aluminium/GFRP structure. For it, a sample (45 x 20 mm²) was placed in a Memmert GmbH 4F450 plus oven (≈ 5.8 kW) at a temperature equal to 150 °C and an optimum total time ≈ 1500 s, and a blade was used to help separating the aluminium/GFRP interface. As observed in Figure 12, the used method allowed to obtain a good quality debonded aluminium and GFRP parts, having a small damaged area on the edge that was in contact with the blade. However, the oven requires larger amount of energy in the process when compared to induction heating (≈ 3 kW, $T_{\max}=250$ °C, and $t=2$ s), not being a recommended energy efficiency solution.

Figure 12. Oven heated aluminium/GFRP samples with debonding parameters of $T_{\max}=150$ °C and $t=1500$ s.

7.2 End-of-life recommendations for the different materials

7.2.1 Summary

This report is aimed at waste management companies and vehicle lifecycle stakeholders, facing current and future challenges related to new policies and social demands. The main objective is to advise and update them to increase material upcycling and circularity, and at the same time being able to deal with multi-material designs for vehicle lightening.

Because of the financial and environmental advantages of new lightweight materials, the car industry is transitioning to them. Particularly in the case of electric vehicles where the weight of the car has grown due to the battery. Then, the traditional automobile recycling methods need to be updated because of the use of these new lightweight materials in car manufacturing. New recycling technologies and techniques are also demanded by modern legislation and regulations focused on fostering circular economy business models.

Nowadays, to enhance disassembly and recyclability, the car industry employs eco-design and design for recycling strategies. In this regard, some manufacturers are exploring the option of limiting the types of steel or alloys they employ to enhance recyclability and circularity. However, it appears that the performance requirements of new laws and technologies will surpass the idea of uni-alloys and the industry will opt for multi-material solutions.

Dismantling appears to be the best choice for enhancing recycling and reuse. The key determinants of whether dismantling is an economically viable choice are the time needed for the dismantling as well as the type and quantity of material removed. The number of pieces that may be economically recovered is anticipated to rise as a result of new technologies that make dismantling simpler, together with digital technologies to facilitate the flow of information reaching the dismantlers.

Sorting and shredding can be used as an alternative to disassembling. The steel and aluminium fractions can be separated based on their respective grades and alloys thanks to new sorting technologies based on XRF, LIBS, and computer imaging.

Blockchain technologies are transforming the traceability industry by making it possible to store data at each stage of the lifecycle of a car part and manage information amongst the various parties. Future material passports will allude to the battery passport that is being created for electric vehicles. Policies and regulations are one of the main forces behind the transition to more environmentally friendly cars and, consequently, the usage of novel lightweight materials. They are also controlling how efficiently cars can be recycled, forcing recyclers to adopt circular economy practices. Future policies and regulations are predicted to place a greater emphasis on upcycling than recycling.

The three Fatigue4Light demonstrators can be recycled if users abide with the guidelines in this document. The lower control arm might be taken apart and sold as high-quality scrap or further reused. The wheels can be recycled using the current recycling system. The cross-beam member should be shred and sorted using LIBS or XRF based technologies in order to get fractions of similar materials and therefore scrap with higher value.

7.2.2 Vehicle metal structure

The vehicle structure can be divided in trim (glass, doors, interior, electronics, etc.), chassis (motor, wheels, steering, suspension, brakes, axle, etc.), and what is called body-in-white. Body in white is the body sheet or frame after being assembled but not yet painted, therefore “white”.

Using the work form Yano and collaborators [Yano_2019] it is possible to see clear examples of combustion, hybrid, and electric cars structure. In their work they provide us with the weight

distribution based on equipment locations (Figure 13). The weight distribution does not take into account fluids and refrigerants.

Figure 13. M-CV99 and M-CV09 are mini cars, T-CV is a small car, L-CV is a luxury car, 1st HEV, is a hybrid, and EV is an electrical vehicle [Yano_2019].

In this figure the engine room involves not only the motor but also the transmission. The NiMH battery of the hybrid is located in the rear interior area while the lithium-ion battery of the EV is in the “Exterior Others” part. It can be observed that due to the heavy weight of the lithium ion-battery the EV is the heaviest vehicle. Following this example in the following tables the material and chemical composition of the cars it is shown.

Table 58. Material composition of each vehicle [Yano2019].

Type of vehicle	Production year	Acronym	Metals				Subtotal	
			Ferrous	Copper	Aluminium	Others		
Conventional vehicle	Mini sized	1999	M-CV99	67,5	0,8	2	5,1	75,4
	Mini sized	2009	M-CV09	70	0,5	2,4	5	77,8
	Typical (small size)	1997	T-CV	70,8	0,9	2,6	7,4	81,7
	Luxury (standard size)	1997	L-CV	69,5	1,1	3,3	5,3	79,2
Next-generation vehicle	Hybrid electric vehicle	1998	1st HEV	66,3	2,9	2,9	6,2	78,3
	Electric vehicle	2011	EV	58,7	4,3	3,7	2,8	69,5

Type of vehicle	Production year	Acronym	Plastics						Subtotal
			PE	PP	ABS	Urethane	Others		
Conventional vehicle	Mini sized	1999	M-CV99	0,4	4,1	0,4	3,3	0,5	8,8
	Mini sized	2009	M-CV09	0,4	3,9	0,5	3,4	1	9,2
	Typical (small size)	1997	T-CV	0,3	3,2	0,3	1,7	0,9	6,3
	Luxury (standard size)	1997	L-CV	0,4	4,3	0,3	2,8	0,8	8,6
Next-generation vehicle	Hybrid electric vehicle	1998	1st HEV	0,4	2,8	0	2,1	1,4	6,6
	Electric vehicle	2011	EV	0,1	3,2	0,3	2	1,3	6,9

Type of vehicle	Production year	Acronym	Textiles		Glass	Rubbers	Others	Unidentified	
			Homogenized	Mixed					
Conventional vehicle	Mini sized	1999	M-CV99	1,3	1,1	4,7	3,3	0,1	5,4
	Mini sized	2009	M-CV09	1,2	0,6	4,4	2,8	0,1	3,9
	Typical (small size)	1997	T-CV	1,9	0,3	3,4	3,4	0	2,9
	Luxury (standard size)	1997	L-CV	1,4	0,3	4,6	3	0,6	2,2
Next-generation vehicle	Hybrid electric vehicle	1998	1st HEV	1,5	0,6	3,7	3,5	0,3	5,5
	Electric vehicle	2011	EV	1	0,3	2,8	2,8	0,2	16,4

Table 59. Elemental composition of each vehicle (g/vehicle) [Yano2019]

	M-CV99	M-CV09	T-CV	L-CV	HEV	EV
Al	1.50E+04	1.70E+04	2.20E+04	2.20E+04	2.50E+04	4.50E+04
Fe	5.00E+05	5.00E+05	1.00E+06	1.00E+06	6.50E+05	6.50E+05
Cu	5.00E+03	3.00E+03	8.00E+03	1.50E+04	2.60E+04	5.00E+04
Zn	3.00E+01	3.00E+01	3.50E+01	3.50E+01	7.00E+01	1.00E+02
Sn	7.00E+01	7.00E+01	35	3.50E+01	2.00E+02	1.20E+02
V	1.50E-01	1.50E-01	2.00E-01	6.00E-01	3.40E-01	1.90E+00
Cr	4.00E+02	4.00E+02	7.00E+02	1.40E+03	6.50E+02	3.30E+02
Mn	9.00E+02	9.00E+02	1.30E+03	2.50E+03	2.00E+03	3.50E+04
Co	5.00E+00	5.00E+00	6.00E-01	1.50E+00	1.05E+03	2.50E+03
Ni	6.00E+01	6.50E+01	9.50E+01	1.90E+02	1.80E+04	1.00E+04
Ga	7.00E-02	8.00E-02	1.00E-01	2.50E-01	7.00E+00	2.50E+00
Mo	1.10E+01	1.20E+01	3.00E+01	3.00E+01	1.40E+01	2.00E-01
In	3.00E-01	3.00E-01	1.40E-01	6.50E-01	1.10E+00	4.50E-02
W	7.20E+00	7.20E+00	7.10E+00	7.10E+00	8.00E+00	7.00E+00
Li	9.50E-02	9.50E-02	1.50E-01	1.90E-01	1.80E+01	4.00E+03
Be						
B	6.00E+00	6.00E+00	2.00E+00	3.50E+00	1.70E+01	1.30E+02
Mg	1.70E+02	1.70E+02	2.00E+02	2.00E+02	1.90E+02	1.90E+02
Sc	2.00E-01	2.00E-01	2.00E-01	2.00E-01	2.00E-01	2.00E-01
Ti	2.50E+01	2.50E+01	2.50E+01	3.00E+01	5.00E+01	5.00E+01
Ge	2.00E-02	2.00E-02	3.00E-02	3.00E-02	7.00E+00	2.00E-02

As	1.00E-01	4.00E-01	1.00E-01	1.00E+00	3.50E+00	1.00E+00
Se	1.00E-03	1.00E-03	3.00E-03	5.00E-03	7.00E-01	
Br	4.50E+01	4.50E+01	2.00E+01	3.50E+01	1.10E+02	1.60E+02
Rb	9.00E-02	9.00E-02	1.00E-01	1.00E-01	1.80E-01	1.30E-01
Sr	3.80E+01	3.80E+01	5.00E+00	2.30E+02	9.20E+01	1.50E+01
Y	7.00E-01	7.00E-01	3.50E-01	4.00E-01	1.05E+02	5.50E-01
Zr	4.00E+01	4.00E+01	7.00E+00	7.00E+00	7.00E+00	1.10E+01
Nb	7.00E-02	1.50E-01	9.00E-02	3.00E-01	5.00E-01	3.00E-02
Rh	3.00E-02	7.00E-02	4.00E-01	2.50E-01	2.50E-01	1.50E-04
Pd	4.00E-01	1.50E+00	1.50E+00	8.00E-01	5.00E+00	2.00E-01
Ag	1.80E+00	1.80E+00	2.50E+00	2.50E+00	2.30E+00	9.00E+00
Cd	9.00E-03	9.00E-03	1.40E-03	2.30E-03	1.20E-02	4.00E-04
Sb	1.20E+00	1.20E+00	7.00E-01	5.00E+00	1.50E+01	5.00E-01
Te	1.20E-02	1.20E-02	4.00E-03	6.00E-03	2.20E-02	6.00E-04
Cs	4.00E-03	4.00E-03	2.00E-03	3.00E-03	6.50E-03	4.00E-03
Ba	5.00E+00	5.00E+00	3.00E+00	1.50E+00	2.50E+00	2.00E+01
La	2.50E+00	2.50E+00	8.50E+00	1.80E+01	1.00E+03	4.00E+00
Ce	2.00E+01	3.50E+01	6.00E+01	3.80E+01	1.40E+03	2.00E+01
Pr	3.50E-01	3.50E-01	3.80E-01	6.00E-01	2.00E+02	5.00E+00
Nd	5.00E-01	5.00E+00	5.50E-01	3.00E+00	7.50E+02	5.00E+02
Sm	9.00E-02	9.00E-02	9.00E-02	1.00E-01	6.00E-02	4.00E-02
Eu	1.00E-02	1.00E-02	1.00E-02	1.00E-02	7.00E-03	1.50E-02
Gd	3.00E-01	2.50E-01	3.50E-01	3.00E-01	1.00E+01	3.00E-01
Tb	8.00E-03	9.00E-03	1.00E-02	1.30E-02	5.00E-01	2.30E-02
Dy	2.00E-01	4.00E-02	3.00E-02	2.50E-02	1.30E+02	1.50E+02
Ho	1.80E-03	4.80E-03	1.80E-03	2.00E-02	6.00E-03	2.20E-02
Er	1.80E-03	5.00E-01	4.00E-03	3.50E-03	4.50E-01	
Tm	7.00E-05	7.00E-05	3.00E-05	2.00E-04	4.50E-05	
Yb	2.20E-04	5.00E-04	3.00E-03	1.50E-03	3.00E-04	
Lu	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3.00E-05	2.80E-04	6.00E-05	
Hf	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	2.00E-01	3.00E-01	4.50E-01	2.00E-01
Ta	3.30E-01	1.00E+00	3.30E-01	2.00E+00	3.00E-01	8.00E-02
Re						
Pt	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.50E+00	1.50E+00	1.00E+00	1
Au	1.50E-01	1.50E-01	8.00E-02	6.00E-01	4.00E-01	1.80E-01
Hg						
Tl						
Pb	4.70E+03	4.70E+03	6.00E+03	6.00E+03	6.00E+03	6.00E+03
Bi	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.40E+00	1.40E+00	1.40E+00	1.40E+00

It can be spotted how hybrid and electric vehicles have a higher amount of elements. The main differences are battery related elements like cobalt and rare earth elements present in the electric motor. The absence of a catalytic converter in EV produces a decrease of certain platinum group metals (PGM) but not for all of them. Electric vehicles have more electronics, and thus PGM in the printed circuit boards.

Nowadays, there is a well-organised business model around all the car parts that can have a second life and be reused on another car. For example, car parts like catalytic converters, doors and brakes, are already being dismantled and sold by recycling companies, and all the actors associated with the vehicle life. Also, batteries, plastics, tires and electronics are dismantled separately. Only the car hulk, or the body in white is shredded to recover Fe, and non-ferrous metal scraps. Vehicles at its end of life are managed in Authorised Treatment Facilities (ATF), following the ELV European directive. There are around 13000 ATF in Europe. Some ATF only dismantle parts for re-sale or for scrap, while others simply depollute and shred the whole ELV for scrap. An ATF can send the remaining materials to other entities to continue with the whole recycling process.

The main stages for car dismantling can be summarized as [Berzi2013]:

- Vehicle decontamination: This stage is mandatory and consists in removing fluids such as gasoline and oils, but also the batteries (lead-acid, NIMH and LIBS). Oil from suspensions should also be recovered to avoid mineral oil contamination in the automotive shredded residue (ASR). Also, the pyrotechnic devices used in the airbag protection systems should be neutralised to avoid safety issues. Fluids recovered can be transformed in new fuels and chemical commodities while batteries can be recycled.
- Dismantling of spare parts for second use or remanufacturing: Selling spare parts is an important part of the dismantling companies business model. Nowadays there are web services, and databases like IDIS (International Dismantling Information system: <https://www.idis2.com>) that are specialised in the market of spare parts.
- Dismantling of mechanics and metal parts as quality scrap: This step is not required by any regulation, but has two major benefits. From one side, removing parts like radiators with a high content on aluminium and copper, and selling them directly to metal smelters, enhances the quality of the metal obtained, and also the revenues for the recycler. On the other hand, removing unwanted metal contaminants like the ones found in motor coils will increase the quality of the shredded scrap. As it will be discussed in other sections of this document this stage can also separate parts with different alloys like 5000 and 6000 Al alloys, or steel grades like high-strength steel and ultra-high-strength.
- Dismantling and separation of wire harness: The mass of wire harness per car is 10-15kg, being copper and PVC the main materials. The value of this scrap is usually high, but the time required to dismantle them is also very high. As a result, it is seldom removed before shredding, contaminating the final scrap.
- Dismantling of plastics and other non-metal parts to be recycled: Plastics, especially polypropylene (PP) can be found in bumpers, dashboards and fluid containers. Bumper removal is usually performed since it is a fast and easy operation. Plastics fuel containers are not so often removed, but still some companies use special treatments to remove safely the contaminants and sell them as scrap. Dashboards on the other hand are rarely dismantled. Other parts that contain polyurethane (PUR) like seats, seatbelts, and other plastics parts, are dismantled only when a constant and clear demand for these products exists. Even then storing and delivering such small quantities of polymer waste, can be non-profitable for the company. Also, the value of these scraps is usually quite low.

Textiles are also rarely dismantled due to the difficulties related to direct valorisation. All these parts usually for the fraction known as car fluff, that reduces the quality of shredded scrap. Car fluff also gets contaminated with copper wires that get stucked in the soft polymeric components hindering its valorisation.

- Dismantling of tyres: Approximately 3-4% of the weight of the car corresponds to the tyres. Therefore, recycling them helps to achieve the minimum recycling percentage established by the current normative. Also, the cost of recycling tyres is usually similar to the cost of dumping as ASR. Tyres can be reused, refurbished, or recycled as rubber granulates.
- Dismantling glasses: Glasses are also around 3% of the total weight of the car, and some shredding companies demand a glass removal stage to accept the car. However, it is not performed by most of the dismantling companies because the value of this glass is very low.

In the following figures (Figure 14 and Figure 15) a typical protocol for dismantling is displayed, where some of the stages mentioned are detailed.

Figure 14. ELV recycling chain [Berzi_2013].

Figure 15. Typical process for ELV treatment. Blocks in parallel can be performed independently [Berzi_2013].

The aim of this study has been focused on the upcycling of aluminium and steel alloys. The BIW is nowadays commonly made of various types of steel (High strength steel, Ultra-high-strength-steel...), as well as Aluminium alloys (5000.6000) (Figure 16). The BIW is based on different subassemblies that are joined together to form the structure. The joining is achieved using different techniques like welding, riveting, clinching and laser welding. The material of each subassembly will determine the characteristics of the joining.

Figure 16. Structure made of different materials.

There are two main types of BIW structures: Monocoque and Frame mounted. The frame mounted one is normally used for buses and trucks. In this case the body is mounted on a separate frame, while the wheels are mounted directly on the chassis. Then the same chassis is used for different bodies depending on the intended use. For example, the same chassis can be used for an ambulance, a cargo van or camper truck. In the case of the monocoque, the chassis is inbuilt with the BIW itself forming a whole structure. Wheels and suspensions are directly mounted to the BIW. It is the most common structure for non-commercial vehicles.

The BIW subassemblies can be classified as:

- Closures: Doors and bonnet.
- Roof structure: The structure above windshields, that includes the headers, bows and the roof itself.
- Pillars (A, B, C and D): A and B are the supports of the roof being A the front one and following by order B, C, and D as the rear one.
- Under body: This subassembly is formed by the dash panel, the FRT floor, the rear floor, the rear wheelhouse, and the raiser.
- Front-end: The plenum panel, the cowl, the FRT wheelhouse, the wing panel, and the upper and lower tie bar.
- Panels, drip rail and scuttle: The scuttle is a sort of channel used to direct water away from the engine, while the drip rail is used to divert water from the windows. The panels are the ring panel, quarter panel and the side of quarter panel.

All these BIW components can be made of different materials depending on the function. For example, pillars are usually made of especially strong steel alloys, while other components can be made of aluminium to reduce weight. The disassembly of these parts to recover different kinds of alloys separately will be discussed in this document.

7.2.3 Advanced lightweight materials for Automobiles

During the last years the interest for lightweight materials to reduce the total weight of the car has increased exponentially. Even more, the introduction on the market of electric cars has put even more pressure on lightweighting. The motivations behind lightweighting efforts, are not only the reduction of weight per se. Improving structural efficiency and reducing the environmental and economic impact of new automobiles are also strongly related to lightweighting. Light vehicles are one of the keys for sustainable mobility since they reduce fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions. For an internal combustion vehicle, a weight reduction of 100 kgs implies a reduction of 0.3-0.5 L/100km in fuel consumption and 8 to 11 g of CO₂/km. As for electric vehicles, those are usually 125% heavier than the combustion ones. In this case a 10% reduction will mean a 13.7% increase in range. With an expected electric vehicle sales growth of 30-35% by 2030, investing on lightweighting will be crucial for the transition between internal combustion and electrics. In fact, on the Lightweight Vehicle and Powertrain Structures Roadmap 2020 made by the UK automotive Council, it is foreseen a weight reduction on the year 2025 of 2-10% by 2025, on combustion vehicles, and 10-15% for the electric ones. These numbers will increase on 2035, to 20-25% and 20-30%, for combustion and electric respectively [Czerwinski_2021].

The current strategies for lightweighting are divided into structural optimization and multimaterial design. The structure design optimization uses size, shape and topology as variables to distribute materials in a component in the most efficient way to enhance the structural performance. Powerful computational software to simulate the topology of each component, is being used together with additive manufacturing to create new prototypes with lower mass, higher strength and stiffness, and better performance against crashes. On the other hand, multimaterial design, it is not only about simple material substitution but a decision tool to determine the best material for each position of the whole structure, based on the specific physical requirements. In addition, the term multi-material not only refers to the car but also to the components.

The multi-material design will be catalysed by the new lightweight materials that are being developed. These new materials are mostly steel, and aluminium based, but there are also other materials on the near future [Czerwinski_2021, Zhang_2022].

7.2.3.1 Steel alloys

Steel sheet metal, forged steel and even cast iron, represent about 70% of the weight of an average car. They represent the biggest share of the market, but they are not lightweight materials. There are various reasons to explain why they represent the biggest share in the automotive market. One of the main reasons is related to the evolution of high-strength steel alloys. These advanced alloys offer higher performances than traditional alloys for the same amount of mass. In other words, they are capable of performing the same task as a traditional alloy using less material, thus contributing to the total car weight reduction. Other reasons that explain the steel dominion in the car manufacturing market are: the steel low-cost when compared to alternatives, its good manufacturability, its anti-intrusion capacity and its recyclability. Even more, steel grades can be melted together and be remixed to produce new compositions, thus reducing CO₂ emissions. In comparison Aluminium is more expensive, has higher energy demands to be produced, and it is more difficult to recycle. Thanks to all these steel advantages, the transition to lightweight materials has been and will be steady and gradual in the upcoming years.

In order to adjust the steel offer to the market demands for lightweight materials, two main strategies have been followed: The first one consists on reducing the density of the steel, for example using Fe-Al steels. The other one consists on increasing the strength of the steel to be able to reduce the mass of steel required. The second strategy has had a major acceptance from the industry. These steels with a higher strength are classified as Advanced High-Strength Steels (AHSS), in comparison with traditional mild steel and conventional high-strength low alloy steel (HSLA). As for a subclassification of AHSS, even though there is no consensus on how to

subclassify them, it is usually accorded that steels with an ultimate tensile strength exceeding 1000MPa are called ultra-high-strength steels [Czerwinski_2021, Zhang_2022, Sivanur_2021, Fekete_2017, Refiadi_2019, Hall_2017].

7.2.3.2 Aluminium alloys

Aluminium alloys are nowadays the major alternative to steel. Like steel it can be recycled and reused in new products enabling circular economy solutions. Despite being more expensive than steel, its growth has been constant with an average of 154 kg per vehicle in 2010, 208kg per vehicle in 2020 and it is expected to be 233kg per vehicle in 2026. The light weight of aluminium combined with its excellent properties, motivates vehicle manufacturers to increase its use year per year. Its density is one third of steel. In addition, lightweight also means less material required which can counterbalance the extra cost of aluminium. Despite all these advantages, nowadays the application of aluminium is still limited to some parts of the vehicle, like engine, transmission, wheels, heat exchangers and chassis. Aluminium is mostly produced through casting-based technologies. The most common alloys are from the 5000 and 6000 series. The 2000 series containing copper present excellent performances at high and low temperatures, being suitable for components with high temperature stress. The 7000 series is currently under research because of their higher-strength properties that could fit for safety-critical parts, expanding the use of aluminium parts on near-future cars. Also, the application of aluminium sheets is foreseen for vehicle parts like automotive hoods, outer panels and heat insulators. An especial mention must be made for the aluminium sheet battery enclosure that has increase by 10% the travel distance of electric vehicles. In fact, the excellent heat transfer capacity of aluminium turns this material to the preferred choice for manufacturers to deal with the large amounts of heat generated by the motor and batteries. This fact together with its performance, lightweight and cost compared to other non-ferrous alternatives, turns aluminium as the most used non-ferrous material for the average electric vehicle [Czerwinski_2021, Zhang_2022, Sivanur_2021, Fekete_2017, Refiadi_2019].

7.2.3.3 Magnesium alloys

Magnesium is 75% lighter than steel, 50% lighter than titanium and 33% lighter than aluminium. However, its cost, and mainly its difficulties in manufacturing and processing has handicapped its implementation in the car industry. Especially its poor formability at room temperature, that demands a manufacturing process at warm or even high-temperature environment. On the other hand, magnesium is the primary objective of many research projects, and it has a small fraction of the market, focused on high-end automobiles. On average magnesium is expected to remain at approximately 4-5 kg per car in the next decades. Casting is used in the grand majority of magnesium structural applications. The most manufactured components are instrument panels, housing, steering wheels, and seats [Czerwinski_2021, Zhang_2022, Sivanur_2021, Fekete_2017, Refiadi_2019].

7.2.3.4 Titanium alloys

Titanium is a material with also low density, high strength, high energy absorption capacity, and excellent corrosion resistance. It also has an outstanding performance at high temperatures, being superior to magnesium and aluminium. The main drawback of titanium is its cost, higher also than aluminium and magnesium alloys. However though new manufacturing techniques, like powder metallurgy or advance manufacturing, the price of the titanium applications is lowering and may reach the market of average vehicles in the next years. Typical titanium alloys are usually classified regarding the alloying elements and purity. This includes commercially pure and low alloyed titanium [Zhang_2022].

7.2.3.5 Composites and advanced materials

Nowadays the main problem for composite materials to reach the market, is its cost. For example, carbon fibers are as strong and stiff as steel, with only 1/5 of the weight. However, the cost is 20 times more. New composites and manufacturing techniques, like additive manufacturing may change this trend in the near future. Composites have the potential of reducing the total weight of the vehicle between 15 and 40%.

Aluminium matrix composite using hard discontinuous particles as reinforcement.

These advanced composites, present low density, good strength and ductility, excellent thermal conductivity, and corrosion resistance. Then in order to compensate the low resistance of aluminium against seizure and galling, the matrix has been reinforced with solid lubricants, hard ceramic particles, short fibres and whiskers. The current efforts are especially focused on using SiC and Al₂O₃ [Czerwinski_2021].

Aluminium matrix composite using steel mesh as reinforcement.

Using steel for reinforcement could be seen as step back when working with lightweight materials, but on the contrary, it makes totally sense thanks to the high improvement of the composite properties regarding strength and impact energy absorption. A little sacrifice on material density is totally worth if it opens a new field of applications for aluminium matrix composites [Czerwinski_2021].

Fibre metal laminates

The main advantage of fibre metal laminates is the high strength-to-weight ratio, enabling the production of materials that are thinner and lighter than aluminium itself. This is thanks to a new manufacturing process where monolithic metal sheets are intercalated with pre-impregnated fibre layers, obtaining a hybrid product with characteristics of metals and composites [Czerwinski_2021].

Sandwich Structures

A sandwich structure as its name implies consists of a lightweight material with low strength but higher thickness together with two thin high-strength layers in parallel, one at the top and the other at the bottom. The resulting structure has great stiffness, strength and energy absorption potential and at the same time, low density. Sandwich structures have the potential of being completely recycled and reduce the car weight up to 30% [Czerwinski_2021].

Carbon fibre composites

They are mostly used in aeronautics and other industries, but some carbon fibre composites are implemented in sports and luxury cars. Its excellent properties regarding strength and lightweight turns carbon fibre composites in a high-end material for very demanding applications. Unfortunately, the cost of this composites hampers its application on the average vehicle market [Sivanur_2021, Fekete_2017, Refiadi_2019].

Natural fibre composites

Natural fibres present advantages when compared to the synthetic ones. They are less dense and had a good balance between tensile strength and cost per volume. In addition, they bring new features, like great biodegradability and non-toxicity which is not usual on vehicle components. Therefore, they had an excellent recyclability and could be the key for the production of new sustainable vehicles. Nevertheless, there are also drawbacks: It is difficult to adapt the existing machinery to these materials, the quality control is more complex, there is an unwanted moisture adsorption and less temperature resistance. In addition, the use of natural fibres is sometimes controversial due to the risk of exchanging food crops for fibre crops like kenaf and

hemp, increasing the price of food which could lead to starving in the less-favoured communities [Zhang_2022].

Additive manufacturing structures.

Additive manufacturing has the potential of creating all kinds of structures, and designs, without the traditional manufacturing constrictions. In the recent years it is being used for a brand-new field of study of bionic-inspired designs that try to mimic natural structures that are known to be light and highly strong. One of the most known examples are the honey-comb structures [Czerwinski_2021, Zhang_2022].

7.2.3.6 Advantage and limitations for lightweight materials and steel.

In the next table are summarized the advantages and limitations that need to be tackled in the future for each technology commented above.

Table 60. Advantages and limitations for lightweight materials and steel [Zhang2022].

Lightweight materials	Advantages	Limitations that need to be tackled by future research
Advanced high-strength steels	High specific strength Tough Affordable Anti-intrusion capacity	Poor strength-ductility balance Springback phenomenon during the metal forming process Defects (e.g., wrinkles and fractures)
Aluminium alloys	Outstanding specific strength Enhanced corrosion resistance Excellent electrical and thermal conductivity Exceptional processability and surface treatability	Relatively high costs of raw materials and expenses during manufacturing or operating processes
Magnesium alloys	Lightest structural automotive alloy (density is less than one-fourth of steel) Combination of remarkable specific strength and specific stiffness	Low durability and creep resistance Less experienced manufacturing technologies Poor formability at room temperature Demand for rare earth elements Relatively high costs of raw materials and fabrication
Titanium alloys	High strength Low density Excellent corrosion resistance High energy absorption capacity Elevated temperature performances High durability and creep resistance	High cost for raw materials, extraction, and processing Poor machinability
Synthetic composites	High specific strength/stiffness Good corrosion resistance Design flexibility Outstanding vibration/fatigue resistance Exceptional crashworthiness	High cost Lack of manufacturing approach to high-volume production of composite components with the best performance yet the lowest cost

Natural fibre composites	A reasonable balance between tensile-strength and cost per volume Great biodegradability, nontoxicity, and recyclability Remarkable soundabsorbing capability	Difficult to implement existing manufacturing, machining, and quality control approaches Unstable production due to the harvest of fibres Undesired moisture absorption capacity May alter food crop market Inferior temperature resistance
Advanced materials	Ultra-high performance Sophisticated and versatile functionality (i.e., lightweight construction, damping insulation, and crashworthiness)	Well-established manufacturing techniques are not applicable Relatively high cost Difficult to implement

7.2.3.7 Joining technology for new materials

During many years joining technologies were not an issue because the entire car was made of steel with only some parts of iron. The joining was achieved by welding the different components. However, with the irruption of aluminium and other materials, the joining has turned into a much more complex matter. For example, steel and aluminium cannot be welded together because during the welding there is formation of extremely brittle intermetallic compounds. Then new methods for joining have been developed for non-weldable unions. In the next table there is a summary of the most used ones.

Table 61. Most used joining techniques for dissimilar metals [Naito2020].

	Mechanism	Access
Self Pierce Riveting	Clinching	Double sides
Mechanical Clinch	Clinching	Double sides
Punching Rivet	Clinching	Double sides
Blind rivet	Fitting	Single side
Flow Drill Screw	Screw	Single side
Impact	Nailing	Single side
Resistant Element Welding	Fitting	Double sides
Friction Element Welding	Fitting	Double sides

In these cases, the joining force is based on friction or geometrical constraint instead of melting. However, if there is moisture in contact with the union, the water acts as a bridge to connect the two different materials, and the joint acts like a micro-battery. As a consequence, one of the materials gets galvanically corroded. In the case of steel and aluminium unions, it is the latest the one that gets corroded. To prevent this effect, adhesives are commonly applied directly to the joint to prevent to contact of water with the materials. In addition to the sealing effect there is also a bonus effect also increasing the high shear strength. Adhesives are produced and developed with the aim of increasing its resistance against temperature changes and maximising its stability for long periods of time. Another problem that has appeared recently, is the use of ultra-high strength steel, because it complicates the deformation and penetration to perform the joining. In addition, some of these materials had low cross tension strength in the direction perpendicular to the shear strength. In order to overcome this problem, the company Kobe steel propose a new method known as element arc spot welding, which is based on providing the aluminium alloys with empty spots were steel is melted and welded to the high-strength steel piece below, sandwiching the aluminium alloy component [Naito_2020, Henriksson_2015].

7.2.3.8 Industrial cases of multimaterial use.

The multimaterial concept in car manufacturing has been evolving during the recent years and decades. Mostly used in high-end vehicles, the trend is now moving into a broader sector of the automotive industry. Being a still evolving technology, that has not reach its final maturity stage, there is not one normative design but many different examples of how to integrate newer materials in the vehicle body. For example, the BMW 7-series combines steel, aluminium and carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). Especially this last material has been used to reinforce or replace panels on the roof, pillars and doors among other components. Another example is the Cadillac CT6, which is built using steel for the centre section and aluminium for the external panels, crash bars and all these components related with the final form and aesthetics. Another clear case of multi-material design is the VOLVO XC90. A substantial weight reduction without renouncing to a strong body is achieved by using different high strength steel grades together with aluminium parts. Aluminium is used in the shock towers, front crash bar, front quarters, and the hood. One last case is the Mercedes MY2016 C class body, which is manufactured with a roof, doors, hood, fenders, trunk lid and part of the body in aluminium. The rest is made of high strength steel [Henriksson 2015] (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Visual representations of BMW 7-series, VolvoXC90, Mercedes MY2016C and Cadillac CT6.

In the following tables are listed more examples of cars using the multi-material approach.

Table 62. Summary of representative lightweight materials for automobiles [Zhang_2022].

Lightweight materials	Typical vehicle parts
Aluminium	Shock absorber, brake, piston, tank, wheel rim, fender, roof, door, bumper, heat insulator, handle, piping, steering component, conrod, rotor, suspension component, bonnet, chassis, spoke, valve, gas cylinder, seat frame
Magnesium	Engine block, steering wheel frame, seat frame, instrument panel, wheel rim, cylinder head, clutch case, cylinder block, transmission case, lower crankcase, intake manifold, air intake system, steering link bracing, oil pump body, camshaft drive chain case, gear control housing, bracket
Titanium	Connecting rod, engine valve, spring, intake valve, wheel, turbocharger, exhaust system, muffler, body frame, engine rocker arm, suspension component, engine piston pin, fastener, lug nut, door penetration beam, car stop bracket, brake caliper piston, pin bolt, pressure plate, shift button, clutch circle, fuel tank, fuel cell separator
HSSs	Frame, body, crash zone, pillar, roof rail, door beam, seat frame, front side member, bumper reinforcement, roof bow, rocker, cross member, seat track
Composites	Bumper beam, body, frontal bonnet, seatback, door panel, lining, insulation, cargo area, instrumental panel, body panel, dashboard, windshield, wheel box, roof cover, floor tray, pillar, rear storage shelf, hood

Table 63. Summary of representative lightweight materials for automobiles (II) [Zhang_2022].

Lightweight materials	Model	Application	
Aluminium	Audi A8	Chassis	
	Jaguar XE	Monocoque	
	Mercedes AMG GT	Body	
	Ford F-150	Body panel	
	Toyota GT86	Bonnet	
	Mazda MX-5	Bumper	
	Nissan Leaf	Battery case, sealing component	
	Tesla Model S	Frame and heat exchangers	
	Ford Thunderbird	Steering wheel frame	
	Chrysler Plymouth		
	BMW(MINI)		
	Lexus LS430		
	Mercedes Roadster 300/400/500 SL	Seat frame	
	Lexus LS430	Instrument panel	
Chrysler Jeep			
Audi A8			
Toyota Century			
Magnesium	Toyota 2000GT	Wheel rim	
	Toyota Supra		
	Alfa Romeo GTV		
	Porsche AG 911		
	Dodge Raw	Cylinder head	
	Volvo Motors (LCP)		
	Honda Motor		
	Volkswagen Passat	Transmission case	
	Audi A4, A6		
	Porsche AG 911		
	Titanium	Mercedes-Benz S-class	Brake guide pin
		Volkswagen	Sealing washer (brake)
		Honda S2000 Roadster	Gear shift knob
		Porsche GT3	Connecting rod
Toyota Altezza 6cyL		Valve	
Nissan Infinity Q45			
Mercedes-Benz truck		Turbocharger rotor	
Mitsubishi Lancer			
GM Corvette Z06		Exhaust system	
Volkswagen Lupo FSI		Suspension spring	
Acura NSX		Engine	
HSSs		Jaguar XF	Inner reinforcement
		Dodge Caliber	
		Ford Fusion	

Composites	Porsche Cayenne	
	Volvo XC90	
	GM Cadillac ATS	Body-in-white (BIW) structure
	GM Chevrolet Sonic	
	Audi A2, A4, A6, A8	Seatback, door panel, lining
	BMW 3, 5, and 7 series	
	Ford Mondeo CD 162	Floor tray, B-pillar, boot liner
	Rover 2000	Insulation, rear storage shelf
	Lotus Eco Elise	Body panel, spoiler, seat
	Fiat Punto, Brava	Door panel
	Peugeot 406	Front and rear door panels
	Volkswagen Golf A4	Door panel, seatback, boot-lid finish, panel, boot liner
	Honda Pilot Cargo area	Cargo area
	Mitsubishi Space star	
	GM Cadillac Deville	
Citroen C5	Interior door panelling	

Then after identifying all these existing cases and considering the current competition to obtain superior materials, it is reasonable to expect a huge increase on the use of the multi-material designs for the upcoming cars. Consequently, a new dismantling and recycling strategy will be required to recover all these materials and comply with the European legislation.

7.2.4 Eco-design, design for recycle: Multi-material vs Uni-material strategies.

In the last section the benefits of the multi-material design have been exposed. However, from a recycling point of view the use of such approach requires additional efforts for the dismantling and sorting of each of the new materials. For example, while it is possible to separate a major fraction of aluminium and steel after the crushing stage using different equipment, it is not possible with the conventional sorting tools to separate different alloys of aluminium and even different grades of steel. In the case of steel, the problematic is mainly due to the dilution of expensive alloying elements when mixing different qualities of steel. In the case of aluminium, the problematic is much more serious because even traces of a metal element can be catastrophic for certain alloys. In addition, as it has been discussed in the previous section, joining technology needs to be changed and adapted for each material. For example, different lasers are used for welding between two 6000 alloy components or between 5000 and 6000 alloys components. Another aspect to consider is the different behaviour of the materials during coating and painting processes, especially regarding processes at high temperature that will produce different physical effects on each material. Modifications to the whole coating and painting process are required to adjust them to the multi-material approach. In order to avoid all this problematic, the automotive industry has explored alternatives to achieve the benefits of using multi-materials without the inherent drawbacks. Research has been focused on dealing with the intrusion and accumulation of impurity elements in alloys. Two main strategies have been considered. The first is to develop and select Al alloys that are more tolerant to the incorporation of Al scrap into their formulation, being resistant and robust against the presence of impurities and even composition variability. Al alloys matching this first option are usually called recycling-friendly alloys, or dirty alloys [SALEMA2021]. The second strategy consist on reducing the amount of different alloys used in a car and therefore their chemical complexity. The different properties are achieved using

innovative manufacturing processes. These alloys can also be divided into uni-alloys, multi-purpose alloys and crossover alloys [Raabe2022].

The use of mono-materials is one of the main Product Eco-Strategies related to eco-design [Schiavone_2008]. The uni-alloy approach has been discussed in the past decades, also for other applications like beverage cans. The concept was firstly introduced by D. Mc Aulfee in the eighties and was conceived as an average weighted composition between AA3004 car body alloy and AA5182 can end alloy. This idea was discarded due to economic and technical factors. Nowadays an uni-alloy is considered to be a single or reduced amount of alloy compositions that are going to be used for different parts of a determined system. For the automotive industry the 6000-alloy family has been usually the preferred option. New manufacturing techniques can adjust the microstructure of the alloy thus changing the properties of it and therefore increasing the number of possible applications of this Al-alloy family. Most of the new techniques are based on heat treatments that are able to modify the strength of the alloy and achieve new properties of elongation and deformability, among others. Cryogenic deformation has also been studied to achieve properties for other families of alloys. All these new processes had enabled the possibility of manufacturing a car with the 6000 family alloy as the only source for aluminium components of a vehicle [Arab2017, Gruber2020, Raabe2022]. The multi-purpose approach as its name suggests is used for alloys that are being used in several applications. Also, when the same alloy is used in casting and wrought products. Finally, crossover alloys are not alloys from the same family and chemical composition but alloys with similar properties. Crossover alloys are used to reduce the number of alloys required in a system. For example, there are crossover alloys between 6000 and 7000 families, that are obtained by adding Zn to the 6000 alloys formulation in order to achieve the aging characteristics of 7000 alloys [Raabe2022].

The uni-alloy concept has also been studied for the case of steel. Instead of employing the right material for right application, the aim of unisteel is to use the right microstructure, for the right property and then the right application. Nowadays there is still no commercial uni-steel. A commercial uni-steel should be cost-effective and achievable without changing the conventional steel process. It needs to be recyclable-friendly and it must have mechanical properties similar to the commercial steel alloys. Finally, good spot weldability is also required. In order to be able to comply with such properties the new alloy must fit every heat treatment to produce a broad-spectrum of microstructures. An example of chemistry for a good uni-steel was based on C, Si, Cr and Mn as alloying elements and Nb as microalloying element. While C, Si, Cr and Mn are cheaper than premium alloying elements like Ni and Mo, the properties obtained are excellent: C is able to boost up the strength of a steel, Si is necessary to avoid the formation of cementite in martensite, during partitioning to obtain enough retained austenite, Cr improves the hardenability, and Mn together with Si and Cr enhances also the ductility. Nb plays a role as grain refiner and enables the production of the HSLA grade. Although all those alloying elements being present in the uni-steel, it still can be considered as lean. Therefore, the uni-steel was cost-effective and feasible for conventional steel makers. It was easily recyclable because scrap of this steel can be directly reused to fabricate new steel, since the chemistry would be the same. Finally, it was demonstrated that had mechanical properties similar or even better than commercial steels, and good spot weldability [Lu2021].

Figure 18. Expected characteristics of the uni-steel concept [Lu2021].

Then again, the push of new technologies and legislation will require further weight reduction, and new mechanical properties that uni-alloys will not achieve easily. The increase in the use of lightweight materials will also motivate the exploration of new sources and the foundation of new companies that will increase the offer thus reducing the prices. Together with more cost-effective technologies like additive manufacturing, the cost-effectiveness of the uni-alloy will be matched. As for recycling, in the next section, advanced techniques for sorting materials, and new dismantling strategies are presented as possible ways to enhance the recycling capacity of the current and incoming multi-material vehicles.

7.2.5 Dismantle vs shredding: Benefits and drawbacks

Since 2015 the European directive 2000/53/EC, sets the minimum of ELV global recovery to 95% of its weight, with an 85% for reuse and recycling. Recovery also takes into account energy recovery. Thanks, to that, nowadays dismantling of vehicle parts has become a usual stage on the ELV recycling process. As stated in section 2, a vehicle at its end of life goes through an organised process of dismantling and recovery. Several authors have proposed new processes to improve the valorisation of the several fractions obtained during the process. Seats, wiring cables, textiles and plastic components had been proposed to be dismantled before shredding to improve the scrap quality and also valorise these fractions independently. It seems that a major grade of dismantling before shredding would be beneficial for the final quality of the productions and thus the economic retribution [Berzi2013, Fonseca_2013, Sawyer_Beaulieu2014, Schmid_2016]. Regarding metal parts, most of them are sold for reuse and remanufacturing, and the remaining ones are sometimes sold as quality scrap. The parts that had not been dismantled, mostly the BIW are shredded. The fractions after shredding can be summarised as:

- Ferritic fraction: Scrap metal after shredding and different kinds sorting (category E40).
- Manual sorted iron-copper components, mostly motors, and electric wiring or coils,
- Fraction 1-15 mm of non-ferrous metals sieved after the eddy-current separator.
- Fraction 15-100 mm of non-ferrous metals sieved after the eddy-current separator.
- Non-metallic fraction: plastics and other materials. Ballistic separation on eddy-current separator.
- Car Fluffs, corresponding to the low density shredder residues. Some copper wires are usually trapped in the fluffs. There is different equipment that can sort by density.

In the following Figure 19 from Willman_2017, the material flows during a conventional ELV recycling process are shown:

Figure 19. Mass flows of ELV recycling [Willman_2017].

In the figure it can be observed how there is no separation of the different steel and aluminium alloys, and copper needs to be picked by hand. The dismantling before shredding it is still limited to certain parts of the vehicle. Then in order to use ferritic and non-ferritic fractions of scrap, remelters and refiners will need to dilute the scrap with large amounts of virgin material to ensure that the presence of detrimental elements does not compromise the final quality of the new alloy. The dilution however will also handicap the reuse of the beneficial and valuable alloying elements present in the scrap.

In the near future it is expected that EU policies will demand an increase in the final quality of the materials recovered, focusing on upcycling and penalizing downgrading. Then, in order to improve the quality of the final metal fractions, specially the E40 and the non-ferrous, two main strategies are proposed:

- Advanced dismantling of high-value alloys parts
- Advanced sorting for alloy differentiation.

The first one tries to go beyond the current metal part dismantling, looking for new sources of valuable metal alloys. The second one uses new technology that combines advanced digital tools based on big data, and computer vision together with new fast chemical analysis tools like XRF and LIBS. That new advancement enables the sorting of different Al and steel alloys (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Alloying elements loss due to the lack of advanced sorting and dismantling [Ohno_2017].

7.2.5.1 Advanced dismantling for valuable steel alloys.

The first necessary step to reach a new level on dismantling and metal alloy recycling, is the development of new information management tools. Tools based on big data and block-chain should be applied to improve the quality and accessibility of all the information related to each part of the vehicle. Information regarding chemical composition, weight, size, instructions of how to dismantle properly the piece and details of the manufacturing procedure, among others, must be available and customized to every stakeholder during the life cycle of the product, including the end-of-life. In this way at the dismantling facility, they will be able to select the most interesting parts to be dismantled by their chemical composition, weight, size, and the easiness of the dismantling. Also, the scrap generated during the dismantling will also be accompanied with the correspondent information detailing, the dismantling process, the status of the scrap, chemical composition, and others.

The next step would be to invest in new tools and technologies to facilitate the dismantling of the several parts of the car. On one hand using strategies of design for dismantling looking for ways to ease the dismantling of the car. For example, the BMW prototype model “i Vision Circular” is made of entirely recycled materials, reducing the emission of CO₂. In addition, it is designed to be easily dismantled, using detachable connections, following its own concept known as “Joyful fusion”. In this way they pretend to facilitate the exchange of materials and components. Another part regarding easy dismantling would be the use of advanced tools to deal with new reinforced steels alloys. Most current cutting tools are not prepared for new generation of ultra-high strength steels. This is also a big problem for firefighters and emergency vehicle rescue teams, that they need cutting tools to gain access to the interior of the vehicle. In this sense, new cutting tools had been developed, like the S700 series of the company “New Hurst” and the especially designed tools “Genesis Boron Capable cutters” from the company Genesis Rescue systems. These tools or similar ones could be used to selectively cut the most interesting parts to be sold as high-quality scrap.

Finally, in order to apply all these changes, especially for ELV recyclers that will need to invest in new equipment and trainings, it is necessary that the new scrap obtained is valued correctly according to an increase in the quality. Otherwise, there should be economic incentives supported by polices and governments to promote the implementation and use of these new technologies.

Studies had been made on the field of the steel considering an increase of the steel parts dismantling. It is especially interesting the work of Ohno2017 where they used input-output based linear programming to reveal the parts with highest potential to be used on different grades of EAF steel. They considered the amount of alloying elements in each part, and the requirement and limitations for alloying elements of each steel grade. The program was designed to minimize a specific objective function. Two functions were used, Greenhouse gas emissions and cost of consumed virgin materials. As a result of the study, it was concluded that regarding the scrap mass flow, the body parts constituted the largest mass among the scraps and therefore they also dominated the material flows. However, when considering the alloying elements, most of them came from the exhaust. Especially chromium, nickel, and molybdenum. On the other hand, manganese came mostly from the body parts. Alloy steel was the main consumer of scrap parts, leaving only a small fraction to carbon steel. Consequently, most of the alloying elements were correctly recycled: 94% of Mn, 99% of Cr, 98% of Ni and 98% of Mo were used as alloying element sources in the different steel grades. Then, the enhanced dismantle and reuse of steel parts will reduce the GHG emissions and the cost of consumed virgin materials [Ohno2017].

7.2.5.2 Advanced dismantling for valuable aluminium alloys.

Aluminium alloys can be firstly separated into two main groups: Wrought aluminium alloys and cast aluminium alloys. Wrought aluminium is usually produced from virgin aluminium, and it contents fewer alloying elements than cast aluminium. For remelters that can reuse wrought aluminium alloys, the quality is an important issue because they need clean scrap. However, for refiners that produce cast aluminium alloys, the quality is not so important, and in some cases, they are even more interested in low quality scrap because the price would be lower. Nevertheless, there is enough scrap to keep producing low quality scrap for refiners and wrought separated quality scrap for remelters. In addition, around 40% of the scrap consumed by refiners and remelters needs to be pre-treated independently of the grade. This pre-treatment step it is usually an important part of the total cost of the process. Nowadays 67% of the aluminium is not recycled, 22% is recycled by part dismantling and 11% is recovered after shredding. Advance dismantling could reduce the amount of non-recycled aluminium, reduce the use of virgin aluminium and the costs derived from the use of low-quality scrap on the furnace. Also, the requirements for alloying elements will diminish. Overall advance dismantling will help on closing the cycle for automotive aluminium. Like in the case of steel, new tools to manage the information flows of the different vehicle parts and scrap will be required, together with new tools for an easy and quick dismantle of the pieces. Usually, the time needed for a piece to be dismantled was one of the two main critical factors to decide if its economically viable to do it. The second factor was the weight of the piece to be dismantled. The heavier the better. Finally, another point of view that will help with the dismantling business it is the redefinition of the current alloy standards. Nowadays they are based on the chemical composition, thus limiting the use of alloying elements, and completely ignoring the manufacture process. A preferred alternative would be to classify the alloys depending on their material properties [Fick_2021, Lovik_2014].

7.2.5.3 Advanced sorting.

Nowadays the most advanced sorting facilities are based on the following process after all the dismantling (Figure 21). The first separation occurs in the shredder itself where fines and light residues are separated by suction from the shredder drum. The shredder drum has also a sieve plank that keeps the material in the shredder until it reaches a certain size. The fraction coming from the shredder is known as heavy shredder residue. This fraction is electro-magnetically separated giving a ferrous and a non-ferrous fraction. Aluminium and other non-ferrous metals will be on the non-ferrous fraction. Then there is a trommel to separate the fines that were not captured in the shredder and an eddy-current separator, to eliminate all the non-metals still present in the fraction. They are mostly plastics. The remaining residue at this stage of the process is called Zorba. Zorba can be sold as it is or be furtherly treated to increase the aluminium percentage from 50-60% to more than 95%. The process generally used in this stage is flotation,

to separate the metal according to its density. According to the Institute of Scrap Recycling Industries (ISRI) a scrap fraction with an aluminium content higher than 95%, can be labelled as twitch [Fick_2021]. As stated in Figure 7, the copper present in the ferrous fraction is hand-picked to obtain the E40 scrap. In order to be E40, copper concentration in scrap must be below 0.25% and tin needs to be below 0.02%. In order to ensure these values, virgin material is often used to dilute possible sources of copper and tin. E40 is still quite flexible regarding the amount of alloying elements present in the scrap. Low alloyed steel scrap and highly alloyed steel scrap can be both E40, which is a drawback for steel scrap consumers. In this sense it would be advisable to divide the E40 category between Enriched scrap (rich in alloying elements) and purified scrap. In this sense, ELV scrap is mostly enriched scrap [Wilman2017]. Ideally it should be possible to go further and be able to sort ELV steel scrap by grades of steel, saving alloying elements and therefore reporting benefits to scrap recyclers [Ohno2017].

Figure 21. ELV treatment process for twitch production [Fick 2021].

Nowadays there are two similar techniques with high potential for sorting improvement: X-Ray Fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) and Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS).

In XRF, a primary x-ray source is used to excite the different elements in the sample, that release fluorescent secondary x-rays to go back to their ground state. The emitted fluorescence can be detected, and it is unique and characteristic for each element. Comparing then the spectra with a database of elements is possible to identify and even quantify each element. Consequently, it is used to obtain the elemental composition of the sample. Despite using an X-ray tube to irradiate the sample with high-energy x-rays, this analysis is considered as non-destructive. The X-rays only penetrate some millimetres of the sample, and it is therefore conceived as a surface characterisation technique, that it can be used also for homogeneous and monolayer materials. It is the case for most of the scrap pieces than can be found after the shredding.

LIBS uses a laser pulse to heat a tiny spot of the sample up to 10 000°C. A very small fraction of nanograms or even picograms of sample are then volatilized into a plasma with enough energy to cause excitation of electrons. In a similar way to XRF, when these electrons return to lower energy orbitals, they emit a photon that can be detected. The elemental composition can be determined through the wavelength and thus the spectra generated. The concentration of the

element can be inferred from the intensity. The mass lost using this technique is so small, that is also considered non-destructive. It is also a superficial analysis technique with the same limitations than in the case of XRF.

Both LIBs and XRF techniques are good options to analyse the metal content of scrap. XRF is usually the preferred option because it has been around for more years than LIBS, but in some cases, LIBs could be a better option than XRF. When using LIBS, it is necessary to use several shots to obtain an average value, because there are variations in intensity from one laser shot to another. Even then the precision is not as good as the one obtained with XRF or ICP-MS. LIBS is a better method than XRF for light elements like lithium, but it is not able to volatilize heavy elements like tungsten, while XRF has no problems in measuring it. LIBs can be little bit faster than XRF obtaining results which when using this system combined with robotics and IA can be an important feature. Regarding safety LIBs is the preferred choice, because XRF is based on x-ray radiation. Special permits are usually required to handle or maintain XRF analysers.

The two techniques by themselves are not able to revolutionize the sorting of steel or aluminium. However, when combined with Artificial Intelligence and robotics, it is a completely different story. Nowadays sorting dedicated companies are starting to use LIBS and XRF combined with sensors, robotics and AI, in order to be able to identify grades of steel or aluminium alloys in each piece of a conveyor, and then in microseconds, send the order to the separation device, creating different fractions of alloys. Combined with cameras and 3d detection, it is possible to sort pieces of scrap by density, composition, inclusions, shape and size. In the following Figure 22 an example of the sorting procedure is proposed.

Figure 22. Example of sorting procedure based on XRF sensors.

However, installing and maintaining all this technology it is not cheap. Also, recyclers need to invest not only in money but also in space to install the new equipment and store the sorted alloys and steel grades. Space is usually critical at the recycling facilities. Hence, companies will need to be properly motivated through economic or legislative reasons to implement advance sorting at their facilities.

7.2.5.4 Examples of advance dismantling and sorting

Implementing advance dismantling or sorting should be possible in the Netherlands thanks to their ARN system. ARN stands for Auto Recycling Nederland and it is an organization that manages the whole chain of vehicle recycling in the Netherlands to fulfil the UE Directive on ELV recycling. It is funded through a fee charged to consumers that purchase a new vehicle, moving the responsibility of recycling to producers. By increasing the recyclability and circularity of vehicles, the cost of the ARN will go down, and also the fee and extra cost of the vehicle.

As stated before, there are some vehicle manufacturers that they are already studying how to make more sustainable vehicles, not only by decreasing the CO₂ footprint but also thinking on the circularity.

Another example of increased dismantling can be seen on the Pollini group. They dismantle through an almost entirely manual process and evaluate each individual part. They send the rejects to grinding plants while the parts in good condition follow a meticulous process of quality control, registration, and cataloguing, and are then stored in their warehouses. They claim of having around 350.000 items catalogued and ready for resale, that are divided into manual picking areas and high-density vertical automated warehouses designed for quick access, space-saving and goods preservation [Panizzolo2023].

The company COMET has installed a new sorting process capable of separating more than one piece per second depending on the material of its piece. The system is based on sensors and analytical tools, capable recognizing various metals connected to the robotized sorting equipment. Their aim is to increase the quality of their final products to be able to deal with the current and future market demands [Comet2023].

Finally, STEINERT, a company dedicated mostly to the development of advanced sorting and recycling equipment, has already in their portfolio, sorting devices based on XRF and LIBS combines with AI, optical sensors and robotics [Steinert2023].

So, there already companies investing in advanced sorting and dismantling but in order to generalize its use in the ELV recycling sector some improvements are required to increase its feasibility. In the following sections some of these enhancements are discussed.

7.2.6 Improvements required for a sustainable lightweight material recycling.

Considering the whole value chain of a vehicle, the first step in order to improve the recyclability of the new lightweight materials would be the design of a new vehicle. Currently terms like eco-design and design for recycling are already common for product developers. Then in order to improve the vehicle from an eco-design point view is not only necessary to reduce the CO₂ footprint and use recycled materials but also think on its end-of-life and how it would be disassembled and recycled. From this point of view, the first thing would be to design the car parts and components with easy-disassembly system, taking into account that a car could have a lifetime of 10-15 years. So, the disassembly system should be resistant to aging and wear due to the use. When selecting materials to produce each part, parameters like suitability for reuse and recyclability. Also, toxic, and hazardous materials should be avoided as much as possible. Modularity and reusability should be encouraged. Finally labelling will facilitate the identification of vehicle parts during dismantling [Gagunov2018].

Labelling is also required when working with traceability tools. Implementing material passports to vehicle parts and also the scrap fractions generated at the disassembly and recycling facility, will increase the confidence and the amount of information available for each actor. The information contained in the passport could consist on the material composition of each part, detailing not only the elemental composition but also the alloys and grades, and the manufacturing process. It would be also desirable if it also includes the best practices to dismantle the part in particular, and the existing recycling routes for it. The label could consist on a QR code that by simply using a QR reader, each stakeholder could easily get access to relevant information. The material passport should be coded in a way that different actors would have access to different pieces of information. Blockchain could be a very interesting tool to manage the permission and information domains. More information about traceability is provided in the section below.

Another good option to manage information it is using the current database managers that are already on the market. The International Dismantling Information System (IDIS) is one of the most known databases that is mostly used to trade vehicle parts for reuse. Just by improving this tool to facilitate the inclusion of parts as quality scrap for recycling and to made it more friendly and accessible to various kinds of users, will increase the material flows of scrap, and thus the interest of recyclers to dismantle and prepare fractions of quality scrap. IDIS could also be enhanced to

include the part details mentioned above: Material characterisation, manufacturing details, best practices for dismantling and existing recycling routes. Even if IDIS become a more user-friendly use, technicians dealing with dismantling should be trained to use this database.

Focusing on improvements directly related to the dismantling procedure, two main topics appear: Training and technology. Specific training to extend the dismantle to obtain parts for scrap recycling must be performed. A well-trained technician will need less time to dismantle parts of the vehicle and dismantling time is a crucial parameter that directly affects the economic feasibility. New cutting tools and dismantling platforms able to rotate the vehicles in several positions will also increase the productivity of the dismantling stage. In recent years, exoskeletons, and human robot co-operation systems (COBOT) had also been successfully applied into manufacturing lines from several companies, and they could also be a good option to facilitate the dismantling. Finally, manual spectrometers would be useful during dismantling to easily identify different alloys and grades. All these technical advances will need special training too.

As for the sorting enhancement, the main trends come from new technology developments. Especially as stated in the previous section, from the combination of new analytical tools with the benefits of industry 4.0. Both for the new analytical and digital tools, it would be recommendable to hire or train personnel for their specific equipment updating and maintenance.

Another important point of improvement relays on the end-users of the recycled scrap. It is considered that improving the sorting of steel grades and Al alloys, together with better information on the scrap, through material passport tools, will beneficiate remelters and refiners. Refiners will expect cast scrap with enough copper and silicon content, while remelters will expect the opposite, low concentrations of alloying elements, especially magnesium, silicon, and copper. Moreover, separation between Al-Si alloys and Al-Mg would be a good improvement. Also, separation as a function of the manufacturing process, in particular between extruded parts and metal sheets. The removal of iron particles from the scrap is another important matter in the case of aluminium alloys. So, end-users would beneficiate from the improvements of the whole chain and consequently is fair to ask them also to make an effort. In this case the effort would be to manufacture alloys more tolerant to recycled materials, or in other words more tolerant to alloying elements and impurities. In this sense a change on alloy classification from the current composition based, to one based on material properties would be a big step in the right direction. Following this trend and closing the circle, it would be advisable for metal consumers, to develop high-volume applications for alloys with high recycled content.

All these improvements need to be supported with appropriate regulations and policies. Current regulations consider only the mass to be recycled but they did not take into account the quality of the final recycled product. In order to stop the downgrading of the materials, and the loss of alloying elements, proper legislation is required. Also, in the case of eco-design, proper norms need to be developed to regulate vehicle eco-design through the proper certifications. Finally, the investment on new technologies and formation at all levels of the value chain should be at least partially subsidized. This including the research on new dismantling and sorting technologies.

In parallel to the legislative push, proper economic decisions also need to be accounted. In this case each recycling company should be aware of their market situation, the quantity of ELV available, the quality and quantity of scrap demanded, and which actors are present in the vicinity of the recycling installations. In other words, they should monitor the offer and demand of materials and the situation at 100-200 kms from the recycling point. Doing that it would be possible to determine the weak spots of the business model and find ways to strengthen them. One possible solution would be to build networks, and even joint ventures between some of the actors of the chain. Another important factor would be the ELV collection rate. Current collection rates should increase together with a better control of the collection. Nowadays luxury vehicles at their end of life are sold outside the EU. Policies and legislation should focus also on this aspect to avoid the loss of critical materials.

7.2.7 Traceability tools

Traceability on the automotive sector is already implemented and it is focused on documenting the genealogy of the different parts associated with a vehicle. The main idea relies on collecting information about the product from a “cradle-to-grave” perspective. Traceability is crucial in a high hierarchical sector based on different tiers. Companies invest in traceability to limit risks and maximize warranty revenues. Traceability is also sometimes required by regulators as proof of compliance with current directives. Regarding regulations and norms, the DIN EN ISO 9001:2015 defines traceability as “those pre-established and self-sufficient procedures that allow knowing the history, location and trajectory of a product or batch of products throughout the supply chain at a given time, through certain tools”. The type of information to be tracked can also go beyond history location and trajectory, including aspects like the components used in assembly. It is common to collect information about:

- Source manufacture
- Place of origin. Manufacturing and assembly facility.
- Production and expiration date
- Number of lot, part, model, serial.
- Components used in assembly.

The main technologies in which traceability relies on are based on Automated Data Collection (ADC). The three main groups of technologies are, the traditional bar codes, direct part-marking (DPM) and radio-frequency identification (RFID). The traditional bar codes are a good option for mild environments, and short timespans. However, for the traceability of the automotive industry they are not the preferred option since they will need to be readable during the whole life of the component. DPM is a permanent optical marking capable of enduring harsh environments. It is based on marking permanent 1D or 2D codes directly to the part. DPM techniques can be divided into subtractive and deposition techniques. Subtractive direct part marking removes material (substrates) from the part to be marked. The main subtractive techniques are micro-drilling, dot-peening and both laser and chemical etching. On the contrary deposition techniques adds new material (deposits) onto the part to be marked. The major deposition techniques are ink-jet with permanent ink, laser bonding, permanent bar code labels, nameplates and bumpy barcodes [Intermec2017]. The main advantages of DPM are:

- The possibility of using DPM to create machine-readable part numbers to identify parts and components.
- Their resistance to harsh environments.
- The possibility of using DPM on very small parts and components.
- The possibility of using DPM to create human-readable string characters to identify the ownership of an item.

RFID is a non-optical technology that uses radiofrequency signals for data transfer. Using radio waves, it is possible not only to read the information on the device but also to write new information. It is also resistant to harsh conditions, and it can be used even if there is no visual contact with the device. Thanks to the possibility of writing new information RFID can be used to store extra information like manufacturing or logistic timespans, physical conditions like temperature or humidity and also verifications or certifications that the part has passed. Also changes on the ownership of the piece if it is required. Also RFID is one of the best solutions for material passport solutions, because a part form all the information cited, the memory chip could also store information for the several actors of the chain. In the case of recyclers, they could contain information like, instructions for dismantle, the existing recycling routes or the alloy and chemical composition of the piece. The RFID device is made of an antenna and an application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC). There are two main types of RFID devices or tags. Active and passive. Active tags integrate a battery as a power source in their structure, hence they are considered “active”. The battery allows the tag to send the information through much greater distances, but the presence of the battery increases the size, weight and cost of the tag.

Therefore, passive tags are much more common. In the case of passive tags, it is the energy of the reading equipment the one that activates the tag permitting actions like reading and writing.

Regarding the reading equipment, it will need to be selected according to the technology used for ADC. For DPM traditional bar code scanner may not work, and even laser scanner can fail. The preferable reader to use would be an industrial imager. For RFID a radiofrequency device must be used.

Enterprise Resource Planning software is also an important tool for traceability managing. Readers provide information and identification for each part to the software, and then the different operators may add additional data to each part. The information can be stored in the cloud and be available to each stakeholder. Stakeholders may have different levels of permission to access the data [Gartner2021].

In the automotive sector all three technologies can be found. In Asia RFID is the most common while in EU barcodes are still preferred. Mostly because the barcode system in the EU is already established and on-going for many years and companies prefer to work with a well-known system rather than a maybe better one. Also, providers apply some lock-in effect strategies that makes the change even harder. However, this could change in the future if new material passports and recycling needs require the RFID technology. Regarding the RFID tags, the AIAG B-11 is the most used standard used for traceability. Nonetheless automakers have already a high level of digitalisation using many tools, to manage product data regarding the quality the lifecycle and logistics, among others. The structure based on tiers forces also the OEMs to keep track on all this information between the different tiers. Suppliers are not usually as digitized as manufacturers, but they are also committed to the use of traceability tools because they must meet the traceability expectations set by regulations and standards such as ISO 9001:2015, EN10204 and ISO16949. In fact, keeping in track the logistics and the production chain is one of the main benefits of a good traceability system. Another one it is related to the identification of default of low-quality batches of pieces. Thanks to traceability the parts affected can be identified, localised, and removed from the market. This aspect is crucial for safety relevant components. Related to disassemblers and recyclers, traceability also helps to increase trust on the authenticity of the recovered parts, hindering the possibilities for counterfeits and illegal components. Finally, regarding reuse and recycling traceability is becoming a very important tool to foster the circular economy in the automotive sector. Moreover, it is expected than in the future traceability will contain information to improve the disassembling and sorting stages even using automated identification tools to increase the yields of resources recovery. Traceability tools are also now in the spotlight because of the new regulation regarding battery passport and future critical raw material passports [Gartner2021].

7.2.8 Regulations and policies

The most influent regulations for end of live vehicles are the ones developed in the UE and USA. Japan, China, India and other regions in Asia and America tend to use their regulations as a reference and therefore their legislation is very influenced by them. In this sense the UE and USA are the ones that set some sort of standard in the field of managing ELV.

Although there are notable similarities between ELVs in the United States and Europe in terms of the quantity of cars, the regulatory environments of these two continents differ significantly.

In the UE, under the ELV Directive 2000/53/EC, which was fully implemented in 2015, recycling targets for automobiles are set at a minimum of 85% for reuse plus recycling and 95% for reuse plus recovery. According to the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) principle, European automakers and importers are liable for recycling costs. The EPR, also known as product stewardship, is a policy that mandates producers to be accountable for organizing and paying for the collection, treatment, and recycling of waste resulting from their products. Moreover, producers must make sure that used cars are picked up (for free) and give instructions on how to properly disassemble them in the EU. The EPR has already shifted entire industries, such the

automobile industry in the EU, toward a more circular economy as opposed to a more constrained company-by-company strategy by giving a strong framework of standards for collection and recycling. The certificate of destruction (CoD), which is a prerequisite for deregistering the end-of-life vehicle, is another supplementary important criterion. To direct ELVs to approved treatment facilities (ATFs), the waste management system and the vehicle registration system must work together. Moreover, the European Waste Framework Directive and the Industrial Emissions Directive apply to shredder installations within these ATFs for light vehicles, meaning that these ATFs must employ the best practices currently available (BAT). With its connected reprocessing and recycling sectors, the European experience has proved the feasibility and effectiveness of legislating to promote the reuse of car components. One of the most recent examples in Europe is reported in France, where the French environmental ministry introduced a bill that became effective in 2017 and required auto repair shops to give clients the ability to choose between spare components from CE loops, or parts that can be reused in their current state or after remanufacturing, and primarily manufactured parts, anytime possible. This regulation was done in accordance with the EU action plan for the circular economy [Saidani2019]. Apart from the ELV Directive 2000/53/EC, there are other legislations that may intervene in the ELV management process [Lu2014]:

- Directive 2000/76/EC regarding waste incineration.
- Directive 1999/31/EC on waste landfilling.
- Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemical Substances Directive (REACH).
- Directive 2006/66/EC on batteries and accumulators, that will be replaced in the coming years for a more ambitious recycling directive to enforce EU circular economy.

In comparison, the United States lacks quantitative recycling targets for the disposal of light- or heavy-duty vehicles as well as particular national legislation like EPR. Inconsistent State regulations are the outcome. Only current, cross-sector environmental protection rules are used to oversee the recycling of ELVs. However, unlike the EU, no parties are specifically designated as being in charge of carrying out EoL activities or supplying recycling infrastructure in the US. As a result, legislation is a crucial tool for taking action to place EoL cars in the proper circularity channels and to stop illegal treatment and disposal of end-of-life vehicles. Considering this, a number of American organizations, like the National Stewardship Action Council (NSAC) and the Automobile Recyclers Association (ARA), are striving to advance laws and gradually shift public perceptions toward more ethical and sustainable methods. The NSAC, established in 2015 as a subsidiary of the California Product Stewardship Council, is moving quickly to draft new legislation that will support the EPR and offer a CE in the United States. Anyhow, NSAC needs active industry involvement and input before starting or considering legislative actions, such working on a law establishing an EPR for the automotive sector, from both automotive producers and recycling facilities. However, according to the CEO of the ARA, the 2018 U.S. political administration is not truly promising new environmental rules, and automakers continue to worry that using used parts from CE cycles would reduce their economic benefits. Nonetheless, the ARA is still pleading with members of the US Congress to move the regulation-making process along. In addition, the ARA University in the United States has created the first eLearning Center that teaches best practices for the automotive recycling industry, including courses like dismantler training, as well as parts upgrading or sales specialized training, to achieve a sound end-of-life management of salvaged vehicles. This is due to the fact that proper education seems to be another key operational driver to close-the-loop [Saidani2019].

Regarding legislations in other countries, Japan already introduced the End-of-Life Vehicles Recycling Law in 2005, due to their lack of natural resources and land resources for dump sites. It is comparable to the EU version but has been expanded to cover almost all vehicles; the EU directive is only applicable to assaultant vehicles and light commercial vans. The rules specified that it is the obligation of the automakers to supply disassembly manuals while vehicle owners would be charged for the treatment of ELVs. In South Korea, the Act for Resource Recycling of Electrical and Electronic Equipment and Vehicles provides importers and manufacturers with a

plan for, among other things, recycling rates, recycling methods, and limitations on hazardous substances (effective as of July 1, 2008). Comparing to the EU Regulation, this Act does not address the issues surrounding the recycling of tires, batteries, or airbags. Finally, in China, the disposal of ELVs is governed by Law 307. The People's Republic of China's State Council established the "End-of-Life Vehicle Recycling Regulation," or Statute 307, in 2001. It specifies the responsibilities of local governments and the ELV recycling industry in regard to registration capital and capability of dismantling activities [Lu2014].

The following table summarizes the regulations on the UE and compares them to the ones developed in other industrialised countries [Sakai2014].

Table 64. A comparison of the ELV management methods in various countries and regions [Sakai 2014].

	European Union	Japan	Korea	China	United States
ELV management system	Law Directive 2000/53/EC Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 18 September 2000 on end-of life vehicles (enforced in 2000)	Law Law for the Recycling of End-of-Life Vehicles (enforced in 2005)	Law Act for Resource Recycling of Electrical/ Electronic Equipment and Vehicles (enforced in 2008)	Law End-of-Life Vehicle Recycling Regulation (enforced in 2001) Automotive Products Recycling Technology Policy (declared in February 2006)	Related law Resource Conservation Recovery Act, Clean Air Act, etc.
Background of the management system	Measures for increasing ASR Measures for abandoned automobiles Environmental measures of dismantling sites	Lack of final disposal sites Illegal dumping of ASR Effective use of resources	Measures for ELVs Effective use of resources Management of information on ELVs	Measures for illegal assembly Effective use of resources Measures for recycling economy	Strict implementation of regulations Environmental conservation measures associated with ELV recycling
Parties responsible for recycling costs	Automobile manufacturers and importers (if the recycling incurs cost), finally users	Users	Automobile manufacturers and importer (if the recycling incurs cost), finally users	No regulation (traded as a valuable secondary resource)	No regulation (traded as a valuable secondary resource)
Target automobile	M1, N1	All vehicles (including buses, trucks, etc.), with the exception of two-wheeled vehicles	M1, N1	M1, M2, M3, N1, N2, N3	No regulation

Recycle target	<p>Until 2006: Reuse + Recovery: 85 % Reuse + Recycle: 80 % Until 2015: Reuse + Recovery: 95 % Reuse + Recycle: 85 %</p>	<p>Airbag: 85 % ASR: 70 % (from 2015 onwards) 50 % (2010 to 2014) 30 % (2005–2009)</p>	<p>Until 2014: Material + energy recovery: 85 % (of which energy recovery rate is within 5 %) After 2015: Material + energy recovery: 95 % (of which energy recovery rate is within 10 %)</p>	<p>Possibility of recycling: 2010: about 85 % (material recycling of 80 % or more) 2012: about 90 % (material recycling of 80 % or more) 2017: about 95 % (material recycling of 85 % or more)</p>	<p>No specific goals (95 % of ELVs enter the recycling route, of which 80 % of the materials are recycled)</p>	
	Information management	<p>Issuance of Certificate of Destruction (CoD), monitoring of target values by the government</p>	<p>Electronic manifest system</p>	<p>Intensified collection of information on deregistration and recycling</p>	<p>Issuance of ELV collection certificate</p>	<p>Information collection management by recycling industry groups</p>
	Characteristic of the system	<p>Based on the subsidiarity principle and the principle of Extended Producer Responsibility Regulation to prohibit inclusion of heavy metals (mercury, cadmium, hexavalent chromium, lead) Domestic laws are being enforced but the manner of operation varies with country.</p>	<p>Automobile manufacturers and importers take responsibility for the recycling No target for the recycle rate/recovery rate regarding the total automobile weight. Thermal recovery is recognized in ASR recycling.</p>	<p>Based on the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) System planning adjusted to fluctuations in ELV price is being done. Operated under the Eco-assurance system</p>	<p>In the End-of-Life Vehicle Recycling Regulation, ELV management is being done with the aim to prevent accidents resulting from illegal remodeling and use of aging automobiles. The recycle of the 5 components (engine, steering, transmission, axle, and frame) is prohibited by the above mentioned law but the ban was partly lifted based on the Regulation of Remanufacturing of Pilot Automotive Parts (enforced in 2008)</p>	<p>There is no regulative system that directly manages ELV on the national level Under the Anti-Car Theft Act (1992), information on vehicles collected by recyclers is managed by the National Motor Vehicle Titling Information System. The Automotive Recycling Association of the ELV recycling industry operates an information website for related regulations to attain stricter compliance.</p>

* M1, 4-wheeled vehicles with seating capacity of nine or less, including passenger vehicles; M2, seating capacity of nine or more, vehicle weight under 5.000 kg; M3, vehicle with seating capacity of nine or more, vehicle weight over 5.000 kg; N1, freight vehicle with maximum load capacity under 3.500 kg; N2, maximum load capacity of 3.500 kg or more, freight vehicle weight under 12.000 kg; N3, freight vehicle with maximum load capacity of 12.000 kg or more.

7.2.9 Recommendations for the Fatigue4Light cases

Using the information compiled in this document and its derived recommendations, it is possible to establish strategies to foster the circular economy on the demonstrators developed in the project.

The following table summarizes the Fatigue4Light demonstrators, and the new materials proposed.

Table 65. Demonstrators and their selected Fatigue4Light materials.

Demonstrator	Reference material	Fatigue4Light Material
Lower control arm	CP800	CP980 / hybrid
Cross-member beam	S355	22MnB5
Wheel	DP600	CP800

Regarding the lower control arm, it is a part that could be accessible from the bottom of the vehicle, and thus not so difficult to dismantle using the proper tools and training. So, the first option would be the dismantle for reuse. In cases where reuse is not possible then there is still room for recycling. The recycling of this demonstrator is detailed in section 7.1.

Wheels are already dismantled for reuse or for quality scrap. Nowadays, the recycling industry rarely send wheels to the shredder. In this case the wheel made from CP800 could follow the reuse and recycling route, that would follow a wheel made from DP600.

Finally, the cross-member beam is nowadays easy disassembled from the longitudinal beams of the truck, removing its screws or bolts. Then this part can be put in the market for reuse or use it as quality scrap.

In all three demonstrators, it would be useful to implement traceability solutions based on material passport, to foster the recyclability.

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8 CONCLUSIONS

- The automotive industry is shifting to new lightweight materials, for their economic and environmental benefits. Especially in the case of electric vehicles where the battery has increased the weight of the automobile.
- The introduction of new lightweight materials into the car structure is creating the necessity of changes in the traditional car recycling routes. In addition, new legislation and policies focused on maximizing the circular economy benefits, are demanding new recycling strategies and technologies.
- The automotive industry uses eco-design and design for recycling strategies, to improve dismantling and recyclability. In this sense some manufacturers are limiting the material they use to one family of alloys or one steel grade. However, it seems that the concept of uni-alloys it would be surpassed by the performance that new legislations and technologies will demand.

- Use stage is relevant for environmental and economic impacts and is directly related to energy and fuel consumption, which are associated to the weight of the vehicle. Hence, lightweighting reduces environmental and economic impacts of vehicles
- For the current project, induction heating for separation of the aluminium plates from GFRP core of a sandwich part proved to be feasible. When a temperature of 250 °C applied for 2 s (sample 250#1) was used, the interface strength could be sufficiently reduced to remove the aluminium face from the GFRP core without degradation of the polymer matrix (epoxy resin). However, manual handling of the heating tip is difficult to reproduce consistent result, especially when larger parts are to be treated.
- For further development of the used process, a temperature control loop (PID controller) should be used to regulate the temperature and automated handling of heating tip or sample should be considered. Alternatively, the process can be trimmed to obtain consistent temperature for separating the sandwich parts (aluminium/GFRP). This can be achieved by ensuring a constant heating coil distance to the material and adjustment of the power output to the moving speed of the coil over the sample.
- Dismantling seems to be the preferred option to improve reuse and recycling. The time required for the dismantling and the quality and quantity of material dismantled are the main factors to decide if dismantling is an economically viable option. New technologies to ease dismantling and facilitate information to dismantlers are expected to increase the number of parts that are economically viable to recover.
- Shredding and sorting is the alternative to dismantling. New sorting technologies based on XRF, LIBS and computer imaging are capable of separating the steel and aluminium fractions on their respective grades and alloys.
- Blockchain technologies are revolutionizing the world of traceability, giving the possibility of storing data at each step of the lifecycle of the vehicle part, and managing the information between the different stakeholders. The battery passport that is being developed for electric vehicles will be the reference for future material passports.
- Regulations and policies are ones of the major drivers on the change into more sustainable vehicles, and thus into the use of new lightweight materials. They are also regulating the recyclability of the vehicles pushing recyclers to implement circular economy solution. In the future is expected that new policies and legislations will demand upcycling more than recycling.
- The three demonstrators of Fatigue4Light can be recycled following the recommendations of this document. The lower control arm could be dismantled and sold as a part for reuse or high-quality scrap. The recycling is detailed in section 7.1. The wheels can follow the current recycling scheme. And the cross-member beam it is already disassembled before shredding facilitating its reuse and quality recycling.

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